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Near-Infrared Photometry of the Galactic Globular Cluster M30

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Ai miei genitori

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Introduction

In the Milky Way, the stars can be isolated or grouped in clusters. The clusters are divided in two main groups: open and globular ones. In particular, the latter are a gravitationally bound concentrations of stars (about $10^5 - 10^6$ stars, Spitzer (1987) [65]) located in the Galaxy's halo and in the bulge.

Galactic Globular Clusters (GGCs) play a key role in the study of the stellar and galactic evolution and the galactic structure. They provide a robust constraint to the formation time scale and to the early chemical and dynamical history of the Milky Way.

Among the GGCs, M30 (NGC 7099) is particularly interesting because it is very metal-poor ($[Fe/H] \sim -2.33$, Carretta et al. (2009c) [13]) and it is one of the oldest GCCs.

My thesis project deals with the M30 stellar population. It is divided in two parts. The main one is the photometric data reduction of M30 in the near-infrared (NIR) J and Ks bands. These data, never analysed before, were collected with three different instruments: SOFI (Son OF ISAAC, Infrared Spectrometer And Array Camera) mounted on the NTT (New Technology Telescope) telescope (3.58m) located at La Silla in Chile, HAWK-I (High Acuity Wide field K-band Imager) and MAD (Multi-conjugate Adaptive optics Demonstrator) installed at the UT4 (8.2m) and the UT3 (8.2m) telescopes of the VLT (Very Large Telescope) located at Paranal in Chile, respectively. The data collected with MAD were taken with the Adaptive Optics (AO), a technology which was developed in order to overcome the impact of the atmospheric turbulence on the image formation for ground-based measurement.

The stellar photometry in GGCs is quite difficult because they are very crowded stellar systems. Indeed, the stellar density can reach 10^5 stars/pc³ (Ferraro et al. (2009) [32]). In order to overcome this problem, I have used the PSF photometry (DAOPHOT/ALLSTAR and ALLFRAME software (Stetson (1987) [67] & (1994) [68])). The method allows to distinguish neighbours or partially overlapping stars with great precision, fitting the star count distribution with an analytic or empirical function, the so-called point spread function (PSF). After performing the PSF photometry on 303 images, I have obtained

two different NIR catalogues for the MAD data and SOFI+HAWK-I ones and the respective colour-magnitude diagrams.

Because the optical data of M30 were available, I have matched the near-infrared photometry with the optical one. The used optical data were collected with both Advanced Camera for Surveys (ACS), mounted on Hubble Space Telescope (HST), and an ensemble of the ground-based telescopes. I have extended the catalogue in the range about of $4000\div 22000$ Å. By using the optical data, the stellar population of M30 can be better studied and the agreement between the parameters observed in the near-infrared and those in optical can be verified. By cross-matching between coordinates of stars present in the NIR and the optical catalogues, I have obtained the colour-magnitude diagrams in the NIR-optical planes.

In the second part, I have performed a first comparison between theoretical models and observed colour-magnitude diagrams, estimating the parameters of the cluster, as the distance modulus and the reddening, and the age: 14.65 ± 0.10 mag, 0.054 ± 0.014 mag and 12 ± 1 Gyr, respectively. These estimates are in good agreement with the literature. Among the evolutionary features, I have focussed on the RGB bump, a star clustering along the red giant branch on the colour-magnitude diagram, due to the crossing of the same luminosity range for three times by the stars during their evolution. This luminosity variation happens when the H-burning shell of a red giant star reaches the discontinuity in the chemical composition in its envelope. The discontinuity is due to the convective penetration in the stellar envelope in previous phases (Salaris & Cassisi (2005) [59]). The comparison between the observed and the theoretical bump luminosity can put constraints to the penetration and efficiency of the convection, which is still one of the main weaknesses in the stellar modelling. Since the observed bump luminosity is affected by uncertainties, such as the distance and the reddening, I have used the parameter $\Delta V_{HB}^{bump} = V_{bump} - V_{HB}$, where V_{bump} is the apparent visual magnitude of the bump and V_{HB} is the apparent visual magnitude of the horizontal branch (HB) at the RR Lyrae level (Fusi Pecci et al. (1990) [33]). This parameter provides a good constraint to the evolutionary predictions. The predicted values from the models are ~ 0.43 mag fainter the observed ones, suggesting a clear discrepancy between predictions and observations, independently of the used photometric optical band. This confirms previous results found in the literature for other globular clusters which seems to indicate a problem in theoretical models at the bump position to be analysed in much more details.

In the next chapters, I will describe the thesis project.

- In the first chapter, the difference between open and globular clusters is discussed. The features of the latter are examined, as the metallicity distribution and the multi stellar population.
- In the second chapter, the methods to determine the reddening, the distance and the age are presented. The uncertainties on the age determination are discussed in more detail.
- In the third chapter, the infrared detectors are presented and the instruments used in this thesis are described. The differences between optical and infrared imaging and between seeing-limited and adaptive optics imaging are discussed. Finally, the photometry technique and the software used in this thesis are outlined (DAOPHOT/ALLSTAR/ALLFRAME).
- In the fourth chapter, the photometric reduction of the M30 images and the cross-matching with optical data are presented.
- In the fifth chapter, the theory-observations comparison is described. The reddening, the distance modulus and the age are estimated through the comparison between the models and the colour-magnitude diagrams. The M30 RGB bump search and the determination of the predicted and observed ΔV_{HB}^{bump} parameters are presented in the optical bands.
- Finally, in the sixth chapter, the conclusions of the thesis project are discussed.

Chapter 1

Galactic Globular Clusters

1.1 Introduction: Milky Way and Stellar Clusters

The Galaxy to which we belong, the Milky Way, is a barred spiral galaxy, located in the Local Group. The Milky Way is formed by three main structures (Schneider (2015) [63]): a disk, a spherical halo and a central bulge (see Fig. 1.1). The disk includes the most of the Milky Way's stars, orbiting around the galactic center in roughly circular orbits, and a vast amount of gas and dust. The stellar density into the disk decreases going away from both the galactic plane and asymmetric axis. The bulge contains the galactic nucleus, including the immediate areas above and below the galactic plane. The halo can be considered as a spherical structure containing the galactic disk.

In the Galaxy, the stars can be isolated or grouped in clusters. The clusters are divided in main two groups: open and globular ones.

Galactic Open Clusters (GOCs) are located in the thin disk and carry out circular motions on galactic plane around the galactic center. They are composed by a number of stars that ranges between some hundreds and some thousands, gas and dust (Castellani [17]). Indeed, it is still possible to observe the star formation in many clouds. The process of formation takes only a short time compared to the lifetime of the cluster, so that all member stars are of similar age. In addition, the stars in a same cluster have similar initial chemical composition. They are called "open" because they have not a clear shape and are weakly gravitationally bound. For this reason, they are going to disperse themselves over time. Their age ranges from 10 Myr to some Gyrs (Castellani [17]).

Galactic Globular Clusters (GGCs) are gravitationally bound concentrations of stars located mainly in the Galaxy's halo, but also in the bulge. The GGCs in the bulge have

Figure 1.1: The structure of the Milky Way.^a

^a<http://www2.astro.psu.edu/users/cpalma/astro10/class13.html>

nearly circular orbits, while those in the halo have elongated orbits. Nowadays, about 190 GGCs have been discovered. Their shape is spherical (for this reason, they are called "globular") and their stellar density is very large, about 10^5 stars/pc³ (Ferraro et al. (2009) [32]): the most of GGCs is formed by about $10^5 - 10^6$ stars (Castellani [17]). In GGCs there is not the presence of dust and gas and then of star formation region. The age of GGCs is ≥ 10 Gyr (Castellani [17]).

Figure 1.2: Example of GOC and GGC: the globular cluster M2 (left panel) and open cluster NGC 457 (right panel).^a

^a<http://www.skyandtelescope.com/observing/discover-a-dozen-clusters-in-the-w102120152110/>

The colour-magnitude¹ diagrams (hereafter CMD, diagram of stars in which the stellar magnitude in a given photometric band is plotted as a function of the stellar colour, i.e. the difference in magnitude between two distinct bands. See Appendix B) of the open clusters are different from those of the globular clusters. The open clusters have almost all stars in the main sequence² MS and only a few stars in the advanced evolutionary phases (see left panel of Fig. 1.3). Instead, the globular clusters have stars in the advanced evolutionary phases (see right panel of Fig. 1.3). This difference in the CMDs depends on their different ages. Since the age of the globular clusters is older than that of the open ones, the more massive stars of the GCs are already moved in the evolutionary phases advanced than the main sequence; while in the open clusters, these stars are still in the main sequence phase at the large magnitudes, because massive stars have large temperature and luminosity.

Figure 1.3: Example of colour-magnitude diagram for GOC (Hyades,^a left panel) and GGC (M15,^b right panel) .

^a<http://www.southastrodel.com/Page03009.htm>

^b<https://ned.ipac.caltech.edu/level5/Krauss/Krauss3.html>

¹Magnitude is a logarithmic measurement of the radiative flux of an object measured in a specific wavelength or band A with respect to the flux of a reference source: $m_A - m_{ref} = -2.5 \log(\frac{F_A}{F_{ref}})$. The magnitude m observed from Earth is called the apparent magnitude. An absolute magnitude M is then defined as the magnitude at a distance of 10 parsecs (1 pc = 3.26 light years) from Earth. See appendix A.

²It is a region in the CMD where the stars burn hydrogen in helium in the stellar core. The successive evolutionary phase are the sub-giant branch, the red giant branch, the horizontal branch and the asymptotic giant branch, respectively. They are well-described in Appendix B.

1.2 Globular Clusters

Globular clusters are among the most versatile astronomical objects. Within our Galaxy, they play a key role in the study of the stellar and galactic evolution. Regarding the first case, they allow the study of the evolution of low-mass stars and the dynamics of stellar systems. In the second case, they provide a robust constraint to the formation time scale and to the early chemical and dynamical history of the Milky Way.

The stars in GGCs are among the oldest stars in the Milky Way. For this reason, they are used to obtain information regarding the formation and early evolution of the Galaxy. Since some GGCs are found at very large distance from the Galactic centre, they are key objects to study the structure of the Galaxy. It is important to determine the age, the chemical composition, the metallicities (that is the metal abundance; in astrophysics all elements heavier than helium are called metals), the kinematics of the GGCs in order to know the history of galactic formation.

Spectroscopic measurements show that the globular clusters metallicity range is about $-2.3 \lesssim [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \lesssim 0.0$,³ with bimodal distribution peaks at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.6$ and at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.6$ (Zinn 1985 [78]). On the other hand, the open clusters have metallicity $-0.8 \lesssim [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \lesssim 0.5$ with a only peak at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 0.0$ (see Fig. 1.4, Chen et al. (2003) [20]).

The globular clusters can be grouped in metal-poor ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \lesssim -1.8$), in metal-intermediate ($-1.8 \lesssim [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \lesssim -1.1$) and in metal-rich GGCs ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \gtrsim -1.1$). The latter are placed in the bulge, while the metal-poor and metal-intermediate GGCs are placed in the halo (Carretta et al. (2009b) [12]).

1.2.1 Simple and Multiple Stellar Population

Walter Baade (Baade (1944) [4]) developed in 1940s the concept of stellar populations to describe the differences between the stars commonly found in the thin galactic disk (Population I) and those distributed in the halo, as also globular clusters (Population II). The concept of stellar population provided the key for the comprehension of the stellar

³ $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ is a iron abundance indicator $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = \log(N(\text{Fe})/N(\text{H})) - \log(N(\text{Fe})/N(\text{H}))_{\odot}$, that is the difference of the logarithm of the Fe/H number abundance ratios observed in the atmosphere of the target star and in the solar one. The choice of iron as metallicity indicator derives from the fact that iron lines are prominent and easy to measure. The abundance of the totality of metals M on H is indicated with $[M/\text{H}]$ and is connected to $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ thanks to the relation: $[M/\text{H}] \sim [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] + \log(0.694f_{\alpha} + 0.306)$ where $f_{\alpha} = 10^{[\alpha/\text{Fe}]}$. $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ is ratio that involves elements built by combining helium nuclei, so-called α -elements, such as O, Ne, Mg, Si, S, Ca and Ti. Metal-poor objects show an α -enhanced metal distribution with respect to Fe by a about constant factor for each of these elements, compared with the scaled solar distribution [59].

Figure 1.4: Comparison of the metallicity distribution for the Open and the Globular Clusters (Chen et al. (2003) [20]).

evolution. In last decades, observed and theoretical methods were developed to study the stellar structure, the evolution and the stellar formation. Thanks to the interpretation of colour-magnitude diagrams of the clusters, it is possible to obtain their age and chemical composition. As a consequence, it was found out that population II stars are all old and that population I stars cover a wide range in age. Accurate and deep observations of stellar spectra of population I showed that they have a metal abundance like solar one, while population II stars have a metal abundance smaller than solar one. Since population II stars are very old, then their chemical composition must reflect that present in the Universe after its formation. Therefore, the metal-rich population was created later for recycling of material of other stars.

Stellar populations can also be distinguished in Simple Stellar Populations (SSPs) and Multiple Stellar Populations (MSPs). The most elementary population of stars is the so-called Simple Stellar Population, consisting of objects born at the same time thanks to the star formation processes in a cloud in a negligible time, with the same initial

chemical composition. The theoretical CMD for a SSP is described by a single isochrone (a line in HR diagram which connects the points belonging at the different evolutionary tracks of stars being part of the same stellar population at the same time and with the same chemical composition, but different initial masses; see definition in Appendix B). Stellar clusters are usually considered good examples of single stellar populations. This is not necessarily true for the globular clusters because they appear, at first glance, close to a single stellar population, but actually the most of the globular clusters cannot be reproduced by a SSP. The departures of GGCs from the simple stellar population are much larger than a simple spread due to the formation epoch or the original inhomogeneities. In this case, Multiple Stellar Populations (MSPs) are defined. MSPs are synonymous of multiple generations of stars that can be distinguished either from their spectra (anomalies in the chemical content among the stars of the globular cluster) or from multiple sequences in the CMD (Gratton et al. 2012 [36], Salaris & Cassisi 2005 [59]).

Since the 1970s, the chemical abundances of the RGB⁴ (red giant branch) stars (they were chosen because are brighter) were analysed spectroscopically and some anomalies were found in the chemical content. The first observations of the anomalous compositions were discovered thanks to the molecular bands of CN and CH: some stars had a weak absorption in CH and a strong absorption in CN band than other stars of the cluster. The abundance of a molecule is led by the less abundant element between two that form it. Therefore, this confirmed an anticorrelation between the abundance of the carbon and the nitrogen C-N (Gratton et al. (2012) [36]; Cottrell & Da Costa (1981) [23]). Another important observed anticorrelation, seen in all globular clusters, is that between the abundance of the oxygen and the sodium: the richest stars of oxygen are the poorest of sodium and vice versa. Although the first observations dated back to the 1970s, the certainty that these anomalies are due to the multiple stellar populations is recent. The anticorrelations in the RGB stars could be assigned to an evolutionary effect (as the mixing of the chemical content due to dredge-up⁵ or nuclear reactions at the high temperature). For this reason, observations in MS stars, where there are not phenomena of dredge-up, were necessary. The Na-O anticorrelations similar to those in RGB stars were seen in stars at the main sequence turn-off and at the base of the giant branch (Gratton et al. (2001) [37]). This result implies that the difference in chemical content between stars of the same globular cluster is a feature of the material that has formed

⁴They are stars which burn H in a shell around the He core

⁵Dredge-up is a process of mixing for convection that takes in the envelope materials processed by nuclear reactions.

the star in origin. The models on the MSP formation show a first stellar generation rich of oxygen and poor of sodium and a second stellar generation rich of sodium and poor of oxygen.

Hence, the authors divide the multiple stellar populations in GGCs in a primordial component (P) of first-generation stars (that is the first to be formed), present in all clusters, and a component of second-generation stars, in turn divided in intermediate (I) and extreme (E) populations from their different chemical composition. The I component represents the bulk of the cluster population. The E component is not present in all clusters (Carretta et al (2009a) [11]). Second-generation stars are formed by the gas polluted by intermediate and/or massive first-generation stars during high temperature H burning process: the candidate polluters are AGB⁶ (asymptotic giant branch) stars, whose envelopes (rich of sodium and poor of oxygen due to some nuclear reactions of CNO⁷ cycle in the hydrogen-burning shell) are expelled and diluted with external gas, and fast rotating massive MS stars (Gratton et al. (2012) [36]).

Evidence for the presence of the multiple stellar populations can also stem from the splitting of sequences in the colour-magnitude diagram due to the different ages and different He contents. The splitting of sequences in the colour-magnitude diagram can be obtained by photometric analysis though the use of filters at the wavelengths shorter than about 400 nm, where it is more visible. The use of combinations of photometric filters allows to emphasize the difference in the radiative flux between primordial cluster stars and the other stars enriched by the high temperature H burning products.

1.3 The Galactic Globular Cluster M30 (NGC 7099)

Because M30 (NGC 7099) is the GGC studied in detail in this thesis, I show a brief introduction on its positional and structural features.

M30 is a metal-poor GGC ($[Fe/H] \sim -2.33$, Carretta et al. (2009c) [13]), discovered by the astronomer Charles Messier in 1764, who catalogued it as round nebula containing no stars. It was resolved in stars by William Herschel around 1784.

It shows Na-O anticorrelations, which imply the presence of first-generation (P) and second-generation populations. The anticorrelations were found for 29 red giant stars by Carretta et al. (2009a) [11]. They divided the most of studied RGB stars in the primordial (P) and the intermediate (I) population, but also found a possible fraction of extreme (E) stellar component.

⁶They are stars which burn He and H in two different shell around the core.

⁷Cycle of H-burning reactions alternative to pp-chain.

Figure 1.5: The Na-O anticorrelation in NGC 5904. The solid lines indicate the separations among the P, I, and E stellar components in this cluster. Carretta et al. (2009a) [11] assume that the first-generation is composed by those stars with O and Na abundances similar to field stars of the same metallicity, characterized by uniform super-solar O values and slightly sub-solar Na contents. They consider the stars of first-generation those whose $[\text{Na}/\text{Fe}]$ ratios fall in the range $[\text{Na}/\text{Fe}]_{\text{min}} \div [\text{Na}/\text{Fe}]_{\text{min}} + 0.3$, where minimum value for the ratio $[\text{Na}/\text{Fe}]$ in each cluster was estimated by eye by looking at the anticorrelations in $[\text{O}/\text{Fe}]$ - $[\text{Na}/\text{Fe}]$ diagrams. The remaining stars are considered all second generation stars: those with the ratio $[\text{O}/\text{Na}] > -0.9$ dex are assigned to an intermediate component, while those with the ratio $[\text{O}/\text{Na}] < -0.9$ dex consists of the extreme stellar component (Carretta et al. (2009a) [11]).

Figure 1.6: The triple MS of NGC 2808 (Gratton et al. (2012) [36]). The red circle and the blue triangle are the positions of the two analysed MS stars, one on the blue MS, one on the red MS.

Regarding to the structural parameters, its equatorial coordinates are $\text{RA} = 21^{\text{h}}40^{\text{m}}22.12^{\text{s}}$ and $\text{Dec} = -23^{\text{d}}10^{\text{m}}47.5^{\text{s}}$ (in the FK5 equatorial coordinate system based on its J2000

Figure 1.7: M30 (Image credit: NASA / ESA, Hubble Space Telescope).

equinox position) and its distance is 8.1 kpc from Sun and 7 kpc from the galactic centre (Harris (1996) [38], updated in 2010⁸). Its tidal radius r_t (radius beyond which stars are dominated by the external gravitational field of the Galaxy) is 18.34 arcmin [38]. The total absolute visual magnitude of M30 is -7.45 mag [38].

M30 has a core radius r_c (radius at which the projected surface density is half that at centre) of 0.06 arcmin and a central concentration of $c = \log(r_t/r_c) = 2.50$ [38]. These structural parameters suggest a strong star concentration at the cluster centre, due to a dynamical evolution of the system called core-collapse (for further information see Spitzer (1987) [65] and Appendix E), also underlined from a steep cusp in the projected star density profile (Djorgovski & King (1986) [27]) and from the high central density $\log \rho = 5.01$, that is the logarithm of central luminosity density (solar luminosities per cubic parsec) [38].

The distance, the reddening (see definition in sec. 2.1) and the age of M30 found in the literature will be discussed in more details in the chapter 5.

In next section, I show the latest estimated values of the metallicity, because the metal content is a important input for the stellar models.

Metallicity

The estimate of metallicity, expressed by the ratio $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, is related to the Fe abundance taken by the spectra of the cluster stars. The values of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ are showed in the Table 1.2, based on two different scales: the scale of Zinn and collaborators in 1980s (Zinn (1980)

⁸<http://physwww.physics.mcmaster.ca/%7Eharris/mwgc.dat>

RA (J2000)	$21^h 40^m 22.12^s$
Dec	$-23^d 10^m 47.5^s$
r_t	18.34 arcmin
r_c	0.06 arcmin
R_{gc}	7 kpc
R_{sun}	8.1 kpc
c	2.50
$\log \rho$	5.01

Table 1.1: Positional and structural parameters of M30. The values are taken by the 2010 edition of the Harris (1996) [38].

[77], Zinn & West (1984) [79], column 2) based on a integrated-light photometric index (called Q_{39}) calibrated from the few echelle photographic spectra existing at the time; and a review of Zinn's one based on high-resolution spectrograph UVES thanks to the conversion relation $[Fe/H]_{UVES} = -0.413 + 0.130[Fe/H]_{ZW} - 0.356[Fe/H]_{ZW}^2$ (Carretta et al. (2009c) [13], column 3).

Kains et al. (2013) [41], unlike Carretta et al. (2009a) [11] and (2009b) [12] that obtain $[Fe/H]$ by the spectra of neutral Fe lines through the spectrographs UVES and GIRAFFE, derive the metallicity for each of the RR Lyrae⁹ of M30 by an empirical relation. The empirical relation links $[Fe/H]$ to the period P and the Fourier parameter of the phase, obtained through the Fourier decomposition of the light curves (LCs) of RR Lyrae. This relation fits accurately the observed abundances of RR Lyrae.

Reference	$[Fe/H]_{ZW}$	$[Fe/H]_{UVES}$	Method
Kains et al.(2013)	-2.01 ± 0.04	-2.11 ± 0.06	Fourier decomp. of RR Lyrae LCs
Carretta et al.(2009a)	-2.05 ± 0.16	-2.36 ± 0.05	GIRAFFE high-medium resolution spectroscopy of red giants
Carretta et al.(2009b)	-2.04 ± 0.16	-2.34 ± 0.05	UVES high resolution spectroscopy of red giants
Zinn & West (1984)	-2.13 ± 0.13	-2.31 ± 0.21	Q_{39} index

Table 1.2: Different metallicity estimates for M30 in the literature.

I adopted the value of $[Fe/H] = -2.33 \pm 0.02$ by Carretta et al. (2009c) [13] in this thesis, value mainly used in the recent literature. It is the weighted average of metallicities from

⁹RR Lyrae are low-mass stars that vary periodically their luminosity due to the stellar radius variation (Castellani [17]). They are placed in the horizontal branch (HB, that is the region in the CMD in which the stars burn He in the core and H in a shell. See Appendix B).

[11], [12], [79], [9], [42], [58], recalibrated on the UVES scale.

Chapter 2

Age Determination

As mentioned in 1.2, the age determination of the GGCs is very important to understand the formation and evolution of our own Galaxy. Since it is not possible to determine the age of clusters by observations, it is necessary the use of theoretical models to compare them with the observed data. The theoretical models which describe a stellar population are called isochrones. They represent the line in HR diagram¹ which connects the points belonging at the different evolutionary tracks of the stars of the cluster at the same time and the same chemical composition (See Appendix B for further information). The theory is based on intrinsic physical quantities of a star, as luminosity and effective temperature, while the observations are based on empirical quantities, as apparent magnitude and colour, which depend on the distance and the reddening. In order to allow the comparison of the observations with the theoretical isochrones and hence the age determination, the apparent magnitudes and colours must be corrected for the effect of those two quantities.

2.1 Reddening Estimate

Definition

Dust grains in the interstellar medium (ISM) have a typical size that is comparable to the wavelength of blue light. The result is that the blue light coming from distant objects is strongly absorbed and scattered by the dust, removing it from the light beam and making the objects appear redder than they really are. This is known as interstellar reddening and must be taken into account during analysing data. Absorption and scattering by dust and

¹It is the theoretical counterpart of the CMD, in which $\log(L/L_{\odot})$ is plotted as a function of the effective temperature T_{eff} , i.e. the surface temperature that would have a star if that star were a black body.

gas affect the relation between absolute and apparent magnitude: for a given absolute magnitude M , the apparent magnitude m becomes fainter in the case of absorption, making the source appear dimmer. This is called extinction. Since both interstellar reddening and extinction are the result of the interaction of starlight with dust grains, they are strongly related to each other. We consider the equation of radiative transfer for pure absorption or scattering (Schneider (2015) [63]):

$$\frac{dI_\nu}{ds} = -k_\nu I_\nu$$

where I_ν is the specific intensity at the frequency ν , k_ν is the absorption coefficient and s is the distance coordinate along the line of sight. This equation says that a fraction of the photon $k_\nu ds$ at the frequency ν is absorbed or scattered out of the light beam on the distance interval ds . The solution of the transport equation is [63] [59]:

$$\ln I_\nu(s) - \ln I_\nu(0) = - \int_0^s k_\nu(s') ds' = -\tau_\nu(s)$$

where τ_ν is defined as the optical depth. And then:

$$I_\nu(s) = I_\nu(0)e^{-\tau_\nu(s)}$$

The same equation can be written for the flux [63] [59]:

$$S_\nu(s) = S_\nu(0)e^{-\tau_\nu(s)}$$

where $S_\nu(s)$ is the flux measured by the observer at a distance s from the source and $S_\nu(0)$ is the flux of the source without absorption. From the relation between the magnitude and the flux ($m = -2.5 \log(S) + \text{const}$), it is possible to obtain the extinction coefficient [63] [59]:

$$A_\nu = m - m_0 = -2.5 \log(S_\nu/S_{\nu,0})$$

where the subscript 0 indicates the magnitude or the flux without absorption. The reddening (or the colour excess) is defined in the following way [63] [59]:

$$E(X - Y) = A_X - A_Y = (X - X_0) - (Y - Y_0) = (X - Y) - (X - Y)_0$$

where X and Y represent two different filters. $E(X - Y)$ describes the change of the colour index $(X - Y)$. The colour excess can be written in function of the ratio A_X/A_Y

depending on the optical proprieties of dust [63] [59]:

$$E(X - Y) = A_X - A_Y = A_X(1 - A_Y/A_X) = A_X R_X^{-1}$$

where R_X is the factor of proportionality between the extinction coefficient A_X and the colour excess $E(X - Y)$. Usually, the colour excess is defined for filters V and B , $E(B - V)$ and the factor of proportionality for the Milky Way is assumed to be 3.1 ± 0.1 [63]. The wavelength depends on the extinction coefficient for different kinds of dust, corresponding to different values of R_V .

Estimate

The reddening value can be estimated by the fitting of the theoretical zero age horizontal branch (ZAHB)² in order to match it with the lower bound of the observed HB star distribution in the colour-magnitude diagram of the cluster. This estimate can be made simultaneously with the distance determination by the ZAHB fitting method (it will be explained in next section). The difference between the intrinsic colour $(X - Y)_0$ of the theoretical ZAHB and apparent colour $(X - Y)$ is the colour excess $E(X - Y) = A_X - A_Y$. Thanks to the Cardelli's laws (Cardelli et al. (1989) [7]), it is possible to obtain the extinctions in all bands. Some authors show all-sky dust maps of the Milky Way in order to estimate the reddening. Schlegel et al. (1998) [62] provide a map of dust infrared emission proportional to the dust column density along the line of sight and calibrate it thanks to comparison between intrinsic colour (correlated with Mg_2 line strength, independent of the reddening) and observed one. Schlafly et al. (2011) provide a table of conversion coefficients from the Schlegel et al. maps. Two versions are available on <http://irsa.ipac.caltech.edu/applications/DUST/>.

²ZAHB is the equilibrium model that represents the beginning of stellar evolution in horizontal branch, HB, where the stars burn He in a chemically homogeneous core and H in a shell with chemical stratification similar to the one at onset of the He flash. See Appendix B.

Figure 2.1: Extinction law valid for our galaxy, described by Cardelli et al. (1989) [7]. The effective wavelengths of some Johnson filters are also marked (Salaris & Cassisi (2005) [59]).

Figure 2.2: Full-sky dust map for the northern galactic pole (right) and southern galactic pole (left) (Schlegel et al. (1998) [62]).

2.2 Distance Estimate

A direct geometrical distance determination is based on the concept of parallax: the star angular position is measured respect to much more distant stationary objects made 6 months apart. In this sense, the distance d is easily obtained from trigonometry (see Fig. 2.3):

$$d = \frac{1AU}{\tan(p)}$$

with p parallax. Unfortunately, the parallax distances are limited to relatively nearby objects in our Galaxy. Gaia satellite will determine distances to stars out to 30000 light-years away with parallax accuracy of 10 microarcsec – one hundred times farther than previous Hipparcos satellite³ with an accuracy of 1 milliarcsec.

Figure 2.3: Parallax distance.^a

^a<http://casswww.ucsd.edu/archive/public/tutorial/Distances.html>

To estimate the distance of farther clusters, the only way is that to adopt a indirect method through the distance modulus estimate. The distance modulus is the difference between absolute and apparent magnitude $m - M = 5 \log_{10} (d/10\text{pc})$, where d is the distance in pc. The indirect distance is estimated thanks to the stellar standard candles, that is a class of objects for which the known absolute magnitude does not change with changing properties (e.g. age, metallicity) of the stellar population. Therefore, the difference between their observed apparent magnitude and the absolute one provides the distance modulus of the system. The classes of objects discussed below allow the determination of distances within our galaxy.

- **Lower MS** The brightness of the lower mean sequence MS is unaffected by the age of the stellar population, because stars in this part of MS are very close at their zero age main sequence (ZAMS, that is the beginning of quiescent H burning

³<http://sci.esa.int/gaia/53198-astrometry-in-space/>

at the core). For this reason, the fitting of this part of the CMD can determine the distance of cluster. The observed lower MS location is affected only by the initial chemical composition. At fixed metallicity and helium abundance, the lower MS can be compared with a theoretical or empirical template MS with the same initial chemical composition. The distance modulus is estimated by the difference between the absolute magnitudes of the template and the apparent magnitudes of the observed MS. This is the so-called MS-fitting method. To use this one, it is necessary to know the error in colour and therefore the reddening. An uncertainty of 0.02 mag in colour translates into an uncertainty of 0.1 mag in the distance modulus and into a consequent uncertainty of about 1 Gyr in the ages (Salaris & Cassisi 2005 [59]). It is better the use of empirical template MS, because the theoretical template MS is affected by T_{eff} -colour relation (that is the relation that permits to transform the effective temperature of the model in colour). An empirical MS can be obtained considering local field stars of known $[Fe/H]$ with distances determined from parallax measurements and known or negligible reddening. The main problem with this approach is that only a few of these stars have a well known metallicity. For this reason, it is difficult to determine the appropriate template MS. A way to overcome this is to shift the position of the MS template until it would have the same metallicity of the cluster. The procedure of shifting must preserve mass, that is the template stars have to shift in magnitude and in colour because stars of a given mass change the effective temperature and the luminosity with the change of the metallicity (e.g. the increase of metal content involves a cooler T_{eff} and fainter luminosity). For not too large metallicity range, the observed cluster CMD shows that the shape of lower MS is nearly constant; hence one needs only to apply the metallicity dependent shift in colour, knowing the relationship which links the metal content variation and the colour one at the fixed absolute magnitude (see Fig. 2.4).

- **ZAHB** A method of the distance modulus estimate is based on fits of theoretical ZAHB for the appropriate chemical abundances to the lower bound of the observed HB star distribution in the colour-magnitude diagram of the cluster (see Fig. 2.5). Hence, the magnitude difference between the observed and theoretical values, where the firsts are apparent magnitudes and the second ones are absolute magnitudes, provides the distance modulus. Since the observed magnitude depends on the extinction, it is necessary to estimate it in order to obtain a distance mod-

Figure 2.4: Example of MS fitting distance determination applied to the open cluster M67. (a) This displays the absolute magnitude and intrinsic colour of the template MS (open circles) for a metallicity of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = +0.02$ and the observed magnitudes and colour of M67 (filled circles). The arrows show the effect of extinction on the cluster CMD $E(V-I) = 0.05$ and the effect of the distance modulus. (b) This displays the best fit of the (reddening corrected) cluster MS to the template one. It shows the obtained absolute distance modulus (Salaris & Cassisi (2005) [59]).

ulus independent of it. Some uncertainties due to theoretical calibrations of the ZAHB luminosity are present. Indeed, the L_{ZAHB} suffers from the value of the He core mass at the He flash (He ignition in the degenerate core of a low-mass star at the end of RGB evolutionary phase). The theory predicts a dependence of the ZAHB loci only on the chemical composition and input physics, not on the age. The distance modulus uncertainties are at least $\sim \pm 0.10$ mag and then a consequent uncertainty of about 1 Gyr in the ages (VandenBerg et al. (2013) [76]).

- **RR Lyrae** Another estimate of distance modulus in GGCs is obtained from RR Lyrae (see definition in sec. 1.3). They are good distance indicators for GGCs. Their pulsation period depends on the intrinsic luminosity (or absolute magnitude) of the star and it is observable by the light curve, that is a curve obtained plotting the magnitude of the star detected at the different epochs as a function of the

Figure 2.5: Example of ZAHB fitting [22].

Figure 2.6: Example of light curve of RR Lyrae^a.

^a<http://www.astro.uw.edu.pl/~simkoz/projects/stars/variable/>

time (see Fig. 2.6). Then, known the first, the second can be obtained by a linear relation (Marconi et al. (2015) [49]):

$$M_x = a + b \log_{10}(P) + c[Fe/H]$$

with P period, x represents the photometric band and a , b and c coefficients derived from fit of the data. It is possible to estimate the distance modulus comparing the observed apparent magnitude and computed absolute magnitude. Since this distance estimate includes the extinction for the given band, a reddening free quantity

W (called the Wesenheit function) is defined (Madore 1982 [45]):

$$W = M_x - R(M_y - M_x)$$

with R the ratio between the selective absorption in the x band and the colour excess in the adopted colour. It is fixed according to an assumed reddening (Cardelli et al. (1989) [7]). The cons of this relation are: the assumption that the reddening law is known and the request accurate mean magnitude in a minimum of two photometric bands.

Other methods to estimate the distance exist (WD-fitting and tip of the RGB, see Salaris & Cassisi (2005) [59]), but they are not useful for the purpose of this thesis.

2.3 Globular Cluster Age Determination

After estimating the apparent distance modulus and reddening with method described above, it is possible to determine the age by the theory-observations comparison. Plotting a grid of the isochrones at the different age on the observed data of the cluster (see Fig. 2.7), it is noticed that they overlap along the lower main sequence and the upper red giant branch. The maximum difference is at the location of the turn-off TO (the bluest and brightest point along the main sequence where the star exhausts the hydrogen in the core. See Appendix B). Therefore, the isochrone, which matches better to the turn off and the remaining data in the CMD, determines the cluster age. The TO location is an age indicator. The predicted and observed colour scales will not be in perfect agreement for each other due to the errors in the colour- T_{eff} relations, uncertainties in the treatment of some of the stellar physics ingredients (e.g. convection, surface boundary conditions), or incorrect assumptions regarding the cluster properties (reddening, distance, metallicity). The age can be determined also thanks to two different parameters, so-called vertical and horizontal parameter.

- The vertical method ΔV_{TO}^{HB} is equivalent to find simultaneously the distance from ZAHB fitting and the age from the TO luminosity. It represents the difference in magnitude between TO and ZAHB measured at the colour of TO. Since the ZAHB brightness is largely unaffected by age, a change of age at a given [Fe/H] modifies the value of ΔV_{TO}^{HB} through the change of the TO brightness: for increasing ages ΔV_{TO}^{HB} increases, because the TO gets less bright. Its location depends on the star mass at the H depletion in the star core: it is evident from models that younger stellar

Figure 2.7: Example of isochrone fitting of the cluster M68 with isochrones of 11, 12, 13 Gyr. The isochrone which fits better the TO location is that of 12 Gyr.^a

^a<http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1086/304879/fulltext/36373.text.html>

populations have bigger masses at the TO and at brighter luminosities, because $L \sim M^3$ [59]. The vertical method does not depend on uncertainties in the cluster metallicity, stemmed from the fact that at a given age both the ZAHB and the TO brightness scale with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ in approximately the same way (Vandenbergh et al. 2013 [76]). An advantage of this method is the independence from the uncertainties on the cluster reddening or on the adopted colour- T_{eff} relations, because the colour is not considered but only differences between luminosities (Degl’Innocenti 2009 [24]). A difficulty in its use is that in many GGCs the horizontal red part of the HB is not populated or HB includes a few stars. In this case, the difference in magnitude is estimated from the ZAHB loci. At a given $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, a 0.1 mag variation in the vertical method corresponds to ~ 1 Gyr age change in this age, due to the fact that TO region is nearly vertical (Salaris & Cassisi 2005 [59]).

- The horizontal method $\Delta H_{TO,RGB}$ determines the age from difference in colour

between the TO and the base of the RGB. This horizontal parameter is sensitive to the age through only the TO colour variation with time, since the RGB colour is unaffected by age for old populations: an increase of the age decreases $\Delta H_{TO,RGB}$ because TO becomes redder. It is better to use it when the GGCs have blue HBs, typical case of metal-poor clusters. As in the case of the vertical method, $\Delta H_{TO,RGB}$ at fixed age is weakly sensitive to the metallicity. Although the RGB colour have a strong dependence on the metallicity, the moving of the RGB location due to the metal content is compensated by the corresponding change of the TO colour: they both become redder when the metallicity increases. This technique is independent of the distance and the reddening, but it is affected by assumed value of mixing-length parameter (α_{MLT} , it is a free parameter related to the extension of the convection) and colour- T_{eff} relations. Theoretical uncertainties on $\Delta H_{TO,RGB}$ (for example due to the convection) are higher than 0.01-0.02 mag (Salaris & Cassisi 2005 [59]), and therefore the horizontal method is hardly used for the absolute age determinations. For this reason, the $\Delta H_{TO,RGB}$ is used to determine relative ages by the difference in colour between the RGB segments of two different GGCs, having the same chemical abundances.

Figure 2.8: Graphical representation of the ΔV (vertical) and $\Delta(B - V)$ (horizontal) method for the age determination (Salaris & Cassisi (2005) [59]).

2.3.1 Uncertainties on Age Determination

The main uncertainty sources on age determination are the indetermination on the chemical composition, on the efficiency of physical mechanisms (as diffusion, convection etc.), on the inputs physics given to the models (opacity, nuclear reactions etc.) and the observational errors.

Chemical composition The original helium abundance Y^4 is very difficult to observe. Many of the spectral lines occur in the ultra-violet and cannot be observed spectroscopically at the Earth's surface. To obtain the strong lines in the visible, the helium must be hot ($T > 11000$ K) and that means which the objects have to be either young or evolved (e.g. HB stars or post-AGB stars). Therefore, this content is not initial one. For young stars, it is a recycled quantity by previous stars. For evolved stars, it is the result of some processes as dredge-up, diffusion, and radiative levitation, happened in the previous evolutionary phases. For this reason, in order to evaluate the initial helium content, the only possibility is through an indirect methods. The helium abundance is estimated by a linear relation between Z (metal content) and Y :

$$Y = Y_P + \frac{\Delta Y}{\Delta Z} Z$$

where Y_P is the primordial helium content, the result of the Big Bang nucleosynthesis, and $\Delta Y/\Delta Z$ is the estimated helium to metal enrichment ratio. The main uncertainty is due to $\Delta Y/\Delta Z$ ($\Delta Y/\Delta Z = 5.3 \pm 1.4$ in Gennaro et al. (2010) [34], $\Delta Y/\Delta Z = 3 \pm 2$ in Pagel & Portinari (1998) [51]). A variation of original He abundance affects the TO luminosity, shifting the theoretical TO location towards the blue, and the ZAHB brightness: an increase of Y increases the ZAHB luminosity and decreases the TO luminosity at the fixed age. An uncertainty of 0.02 on the helium content can involve an uncertainty of 8%-9% on the age of old clusters and of 5% for intermediate age clusters (Degl'Innocenti 2009 [24]).

From numerical models, it is noticed that an uncertainty in $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ of the order of 0.1 dex leads to an age variation of $\sim 2\%$ for old clusters and of $\sim 5\%$ for intermediate age clusters (Degl'Innocenti 2009 [24]). An over-abundance of α -elements (such as C, O, Ne, Mg, Si, S, Ar, Ca, Ti, that is the elements synthesized by alpha capture reactions) with respect to the solar mixture (so-called α -enhancement) leads to a variation of the evolutionary characteristics.

⁴In stellar astrophysics, the symbols X , Y and Z indicate the mass fractions of hydrogen, helium and all other elements heavier than helium (called metals) respectively; these three parameters are related through the normalization $X+Y+Z=1$.

Input physics Age determination is influenced by the H and He burning cross sections and the opacity. They are so-called input physics of the theoretical models. The uncertainties on the pp chain and CNO cycle (set of reactions for H burning) cross sections are driven by reactions with lowest cross sections: ${}^1\text{H}(p, \nu_e e^+){}^2\text{H}$ and ${}^{14}\text{N}(p, \gamma){}^{15}\text{O}$, respectively. For ${}^1\text{H}(p, \nu_e e^+){}^2\text{H}$ an uncertainty of about 3% is assumed (Valle et al. (2013) [73]). The ${}^{14}\text{N}(p, \gamma){}^{15}\text{O}$ cross section can lead to an uncertainty of 10% (Valle et al. (2013) [73]). Regarding 3α (set of reactions of He burning) cross section uncertainty, it is assumed to be about 15%. These effects are negligible on age estimate (Degl’Innocenti 2009 [24]).

Regarding to the opacity, it can distinguish in radiative and conductive one. The first represents the ability of the stellar material to absorb the radiation thanks to some photon-material interactions as Thomson scattering, bound-bound (absorption by an electron bound to an ion), bound-free (photoionization) and free-free (inverse bremsstrahlung) processes. Instead, the conductive opacity is related to the electron conductive transport that becomes dominant in the dense degenerate regions in the stellar interiors due to the electronic degeneracy. The radiative opacity uncertainty for the MS and the central He-burning stars is 5% (Valle et al. (2013) [73]), negligible for the age variation. On the other hand, the conductive opacity has a stronger influence on the He core mass at the helium ignition for the old clusters, because these stars develop an electronic degenerate core during the RGB phase and therefore the thermal electron conduction contributes significantly to the energy transport, and thus on the HB luminosity. Valle et al. (2013) [73] assume an uncertainty of 5%. The maximum variation of the conductive opacity on the age determination is 0.6 Gyr [24].

Another source of the uncertainty is the neutrinos emission. At the high temperature and density, several processes of emission of neutrinos are efficient and they provide energy loss channels in the stellar interiors, with the consequent effect on the stellar structures. During the RGB phase in the dense and not extremely hot helium core, the neutrino losses are dominated by the plasma neutrino emission process, $\gamma_p \rightarrow \nu + \bar{\nu}$, whose efficiency affects important quantities of the RGB evolution (i.e. He core mass, stellar luminosity at the helium flash). The effect of a variation of the plasma neutrino energy losses has an uncertainty of $\sim 4\%$, negligible for the age determination (Valle et al. (2013) [73]).

Physical mechanisms The diffusion is a transport mechanism of the matter which consists in a net movement of the atoms or molecules, due to the concentration and pressure gradients and radiative forces. A concentration diffusion process leads each element to the stellar regions where it is present in lower quantities. Due to the H-burning in helium in

the main sequence, the effect of the concentration gradient is that to carry the hydrogen towards the inner regions and the helium towards the outer ones. The pressure gradient, linked to the gravity, is the responsible of the gravitational diffusive sedimentation which leads the heavy elements to the central regions at the different depths depending on the molecular weight: in a MS star, H goes up in the surface and He and metals go down towards the interior layers. Finally, the photons of the radiative flux transmit impulse to the particles which are led to the outer regions. Diffusion of the helium and the heavy elements occurs on a timescale of a few Gyrs, so it is important only for old clusters. The diffusion tends to vary the position of Turn-Off (TO) and Zero Age Horizontal Branch (ZAHB) stars. He sedimentation towards the center of star increases the central temperature and the H burning efficiency, and decreases the luminosity of the turn off (TO). In addition, it leads to the early onset of 3α reactions due to increasing central temperature and then to the lower core He mass and the lower HB luminosity. The uncertainties in the predicted magnitudes of TO and ZAHB are due to the uncertainties in the efficiency of element sedimentation in low mass, metal poor stars. For ages of the order of 10 Gyr, the uncertainties in sedimentation affect the calibration of the TO luminosity in terms of cluster ages less than 1 Gyr. However, this uncertainty becomes larger for older cluster ages. Since the variation in the TO luminosity is partially balanced by a similar variation of ZAHB luminosities, the vertical method appears less affected by sedimentation (Castellani & Degl’Innocenti (1999) [18]). The estimated uncertainty for diffusion velocities is of the order to $10\div 15\%$ (Valle et al. (2013) [73], Degl’Innocenti (2009) [24]). Another source of the uncertainty is the extension of the convection transport. The convection is a mechanism of energy transport that involves motions of the matter on the large scale in the stellar interior. Under certain conditions given the Schwarzschild criterion,⁵ the small random perturbations of the gas elements can extend on large-scale: the hot matter may rise to the outer layers, where it cools, and falls down as cold material. The mean free path of a convective element is so-called mixing length and is defined as $l_c = \alpha_{MLT} H_P$, where $H_P^{-1} = -d\ln P/dr$ is the pressure scale height and α_{MLT} is a free parameter calibrated empirically [59]. The convective element can continue to rise over the limit boundary under which the Schwarzschild criterion is valid, because it has a non-negligible velocity. This process is called overshooting. It represents a source of

⁵The Schwarzschild criterion is $\nabla_{rad} > \nabla_{ad}$, where ∇_{rad} is the radiative temperature gradient (i.e that of the environment if the convection is not present) and ∇_{ad} is the adiabatic temperature gradient (i.e. that of the convective bubble assuming the adiabatic approximation). Therefore the temperature of the bubble after a displacement Δr towards the stellar surface is higher than the environment, its density is lower and consequently it will receive an acceleration towards the surface. It give the condition for the onset of the convection. See Appendix C.

uncertainty, because an accurate theoretical determination of this effect is still unavailable. In the stellar convective core,⁶ the overshooting carries fuel in the nuclear fusion regions, extending the lifetime of the star in the main sequence and changing the age. The overshooting affects the age determination in the age range $\sim 1 \text{ Gyr} (\pm 20\%) \div 3 \text{ Gyr} (\pm 10\%)$ [24].

Observational errors The main observational problems are the determination of the cluster reddening and the definition of turn-off luminosity for the using of vertical method, because TO region on the CMD is almost vertical. Some authors try to circumvent this problem using the magnitude of a point close to the TO but 0.05 mag redder, either on the MS or on the SGB.

Finally, the main sources of uncertainty for the age determination for old clusters are the diffusion efficiency, the original helium abundance, the opacity and observational errors. Adding the errors in quadrature leads to a total uncertainty of $\sim 1.5 \text{ Gyr}$ (Degl’Innocenti 2009 [24]).

⁶The convective temperature gradient is proportional to the opacity and energy flux. The star with a high central temperature burns the fuel in the core through the more efficient mechanisms of energy production and then the energy flux is larger. This establishes the onset of the convection.

Chapter 3

Instruments and Imaging

3.1 IR Arrays

Detectors used in infrared astronomy are different in operation than CCDs (Charge Coupled Devices) used in optical astronomy, but the physical base is the same for both. Infrared detectors are made from semiconductors with a small energy gap between the valence band and the conduction band. Incident photons excite the electrons into the valence band and move them into the conduction one. Therefore, these IR detectors absorb the incoming radiation and convert it in conducting electrons. The output signal depends on the distribution of electrical energy (Rogalski (2002) [57]).

The electrons can be excited not only by incoming photons, but also by thermal energy. This can generate the dark current. For this reason, the IR detectors and instrumental optics must operate at low temperatures to achieve high sensibility, in inverse proportion to the wavelength response of the detector material (Joyce (1992) [40]). The detector, due to the dependence of the thermal background on the ambient environment, has to be cooled and isolated by cold surface.

IR array materials are not made to operate simultaneously as detectors and readout chip, unlike the CCD devices. In order to solve this problem the hybrid arrays are used. This type of array have semiconductor detector and readout circuit built separately and linked mechanically and electronically through an interconnection (see Fig. 3.1). The detector array is a p-n junction, formed by a substrate of n-type and a p-type region for each pixel. It creates a potential if it is hit from incident radiation. The readout array consists of a Si chip, formed by rows and columns of an address decoder and an output amplifier (Joyce (1992) [40]). The important advantage is that each pixel is isolated from its neighbours. This resolves the CCD problem of "blooming", that is a overflowing of

photoelectrons from a saturated pixel to neighbors, and that of "charge trail", that is the loss of charge during the reading process.

Figure 3.1: Hybrid IR array: (a) (b) indium bump technique, (c) loophole technique, where the detector and the readout chips are glued together to form a single chip [Rogalski (2002) [57]]. Nowadays, one of the most used arrays is that with base of HgCdTe (e.g. Hawaii HgCdTe).

3.1.1 Readout mode

Each pixel of the detector operates as a capacitor C and the readout circuit measures the generated potential on it, related to the charge collected by capacitance. The relation between voltage and charge is assumed linear; obviously, it is not true for saturated pixels.

The reading process is not destructive, then it can be made at any time. At the beginning of integration, the voltage is set at the bias level. Later, only one pixel row of the address decoder is activated at the time and every pixel in the selected row is connected to a different column of circuit, which in turn it is connected via a reset switch to output amplifier. After the opening of reset switch, the voltage shifts to a new value and then increases linearly with time, until the pixel saturates or is rebased. The offset after biasing is proportional to $\sqrt{k_B T / C}$ (that is the thermal noise on the capacitor) and is

an random uncertainty in charge on the capacitor, so the offset varies in amplitude (Joyce (1992) [40]).

Figure 3.2: Representation of different readout technique. The dots represent when the voltage is sampled (more readout are permitted because the readout process is not destructive) [Joyce (1992) [40]].

Different readout techniques exist (they are showed in Fig. 3.2) and the most used one is "double correlated sampling" (DCS), in which the signal is sampled twice, after the first reset and before the subsequent one. The integration time is the interval between the two reads and the signal is the voltage difference. This technique removes the kTC noise, but at the cost of $\sqrt{2}$ in read noise, because two readouts are made (Joyce (1992) [40]).

3.2 Earth's Atmosphere feature

The Earth's atmosphere puts several limitations to ground-based telescopes. The main reasons are: absorption of the incoming photons, background radiation, scattering and atmosphere turbulence.

The regions of the electromagnetic spectrum to whose the Earth's atmosphere is mostly transparent are the entire visible region (390 nm-780 nm), the near ultraviolet, the near infrared, mid infrared and radio wavebands.

Figure 3.3: Transmission of the atmosphere.^a

^ahttp://blair.pha.jhu.edu/spectroscopy/atm_trans.html

The absorption of light is caused by the interaction between the photons and the atoms and molecules present in the atmosphere. In the Infrared, the absorption is characterized by a series of narrow windows along which the atmosphere is transparent, at $1.25 \mu\text{m}$ (*J*-band), $1.6 \mu\text{m}$ (*H*-band), $2.2 \mu\text{m}$ (*K*-band) and $3.4 \mu\text{m}$ (*L*-band), interrupted by a series of wide bands of absorption due to oxygen and water vapour.

The brightness of the background radiation of the atmosphere affects the observation of the objects: source fainter than this background cannot be detected, while source close to this limit needs a long exposure time. The main causes of this problem are the Moon and emission from OH.

Atmosphere scattering is caused by the molecules and by aerosols in the air. The vertical distribution of these particles depends on different factors as wind, climate, pollution. The molecular scattering is Rayleigh scattering, because the dimensions of the molecules are shorter than wavelength of IR radiation, while aerosol scattering is Mie scattering because the particles which make up it are bigger than molecules.

The atmosphere turbulence is due to the injection of energy in the atmosphere from solar heating. Several airmasses move in different directions with different velocities. Turbulence can be produced at different scales: on small scales (from ground to 1km) the surface irregularity generates small eddies which exchange heating between ground and atmosphere; on middle scales (1km-10km) wind, updrafts, convection produce eddies which play a key role in the refractive index variations; on big scales (a few tens of meter up to few km) where there are strong wind shear that produce strong turbulence and pressure gradients (see for all references of this section: Marafatto (2016) [46] and Lena et al. (1988) [43]).

3.2.1 The IR Sky

Observations in the IR are more complicated than optical ones, because the IR sky background is more variable than one observed in optical bands. This is due to stronger atmospheric absorption and emission throughout the IR wavelength region.

The IR window is ranged from 1 to 2.5 μm (SOFI User's manual [44]). For wavelengths shorter than 2.3 μm , the background is dominated by non-thermal emission, principally aurora, OH and O₂ emission lines. These lines are stronger just after sunset and weaker after midnight.

For wavelengths longer than of 2.3 μm , the background is dominated by thermal emission from the telescope and the sky.

3.3 Optical and IR Imaging

The main difference between the optical and the infrared imaging is due to some constraints: optical imaging is mainly limited by the signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) of individual images, while the IR imaging is mainly limited by the fluctuation of the sky background. In the first case, the imaging is called signal-to-noise limited; in the second case, it is called sky-limited. The signal to noise ratio is defined by (Howell 2006 [39]):

$$S/N = \frac{S_*t}{\sqrt{S_*t + n_{pix}(N_S t + N_D t + N_R^2)}} \quad (3.1)$$

The different contributions at the noise are added in quadrature (these are based on Poissonian statistics, except N_R). The terms in the equation are the count rate in electron per second S_* , the integration time t , the total number of the photons from the sky N_S , the total number of the dark current electrons per pixel N_D , the total number of the electrons per pixel resulting by the read out noise N_R and the number of the pixels under consideration n_{pix} . The noise terms which dominate are read out noise at the short exposure time and the brightness of the sky background at the long exposure time (if the thermal current is made negligible cooling the structure). The reduction technique are different for two types of imaging. In the optical, it is necessary to optimize the signal to noise ratio, minimizing the denominator of the Eq. 3.1. In the infrared, it is necessary to lower the sky level, subtracting it from the object image. The Sky subtraction is made taking a frame of the background. This frame can be obtained in two different ways:

- The telescope can be pointed on a sky region free from light sources. The sky frame is taken in the same conditions of the target frame.
- A different approach is given by the dithering technique. The telescope is moved a small amount in consecutive exposures, in the regions near the target. The frames obtained with the dithering technique are averaged among them.

3.4 Seeing-limited Imaging and Adaptive Optics

The angular resolution of a telescope is limited by diffraction (intrinsic physical limit), atmospheric turbulence, imperfections in the lenses and misalignment. If optical system is able to produce images with angular resolution as good as the instrument theoretical limit, then it is said to be diffraction-limited. The diffraction is caused by the finite size of the telescope because it collects only a portion of the radiation of astronomical objects. A theoretical diffraction-limited image formed through a circular aperture is a light spot, composed by a central bright disk (so-called Airy disk) with a series of concentric light ring, having a Full Width Half Maximum (FWHM) in radians of $FWHM = 1.03\lambda/D$ (Howell 2006 [39]), where λ is the observed wavelength and D is the diameter of the aperture. If the radius of the first Airy disk dark ring is used as image size, the formula is $r = 1.22\lambda/D$ (Howell 2006 [39]).

Since the stellar objects are very far from Earth, the incoming wavefront can be approximated as a one of plane wave. The atmosphere turbulence distorts the wavefront, changing its geometry in chaotic way and creating the blurring and twinkling of astronomical objects. It causes variations of the optical refractive index and hence of the wavefront. This phenomenon is known as seeing and perturbs the images seen through the telescope. A seeing measurement is the FWHM of the point spread function.¹ The main parameters that characterize it are:

- Fried radius r_0 , which is the average dimension of a turbulent bubble $\propto \lambda^{6/5}$ (Lena (1988) [43]). If the diameter D of the aperture is smaller than r_0 then the telescope is less affected by seeing than diffraction. If $D > r_0$ then the seeing dominates and the resolution will be limited to λ/r_0 (disk of seeing). Since the Fried radius increases with λ , it will be bigger in infrared, therefore the resolution will be better and the seeing-limited will improve.
- Isoplanatic patch θ_0 , that is the angle subtended within Field Of View (FoV)²

¹It is the output function of the detector that describes a point source.

²FoV is the area of sky seen through the telescope.

inside which the wavefront phase varies less than one radian; the maximum angle of separation between two sources inside which the delay effects of wavefront phases are the same. It is $\theta_0 \sim 0.314 \cos(z) r_0 / H$ ([46], [1]), where z is the zenithal distance and H is altitude of turbulent layers.

- Coherence time τ_0 is the time scale in which the wavefront phase varies by 1 rad within θ_0 and measures the time scale of variability of turbulence. It is $\tau_0 = r_0 / \nu$ ([46], [1]), where ν is the wind velocity. If the exposure time is shorter than τ_0 , then the speckles are formed in the image, generated by interference among coherent lights coming from different part of telescope pupil. These speckles have the angular dimension equal to λ / D , that is the resolving power of the telescope. When the exposure time is longer than the coherence time, the speckles move, because the turbulence along the line of sight of the telescope has changed structure. In this case, the disk of seeing is formed and its angular size is λ / r_0 .

To fully exploit the potential of modern telescopes, it is necessary to overcome the effects of the atmospheric turbulence. The construction of a telescope out of the atmosphere removes the seeing problem, but adds the problem of the a high cost. Furthermore, due to the difficulty to carry large objects in orbit, the diameter of a space telescope is smaller than a ground-based telescope, therefore the stored quantity of light is lower. The goal of Adaptive Optics (AO) is to reduce the distortions introduced from the atmosphere on the wavefront of a scientific object, producing an equal and opposite distortion, and move close as much as possible to the diffraction-limited. Diffraction limited can be accomplished with adaptive optics only for longer wavelengths. This is a technological limit: the pistons of the deformable mirrors (see definition below) should move at higher frequency in order to correct the variation of the wavefront in short wavelengths. In addition, the deformable mirrors should be able to have variations on spatial scales smaller than those in infrared. This involves a high density of the pistons in the mirrors. The main parts of AO system are the wavefront sensor (WFS), the control system, compensating mirrors and beam-splitter. These instruments are operated in closed-loop (Andersen & Enmark (2011) [71]) shown in Fig. 3.4:

- The perturbed wavefront incomes on a deformable mirror. It consists of an actuator array connected to a thin optical surface which can deform itself. This deformation compensates for the phase differences introduced by the turbulence and the telescope.
- The light goes through a beam-splitter, which divides it in two parts, one spent

to the IR detector (infrared wavelengths) and other one to the wavefront sensor (optical wavelengths). The latter is formed by a phase-sensitive optical device and by a low noise, high efficiency quantum, photon detector.

- The wavefront sensor measures the phase errors of the incident radiation on the focal plane coming from deformable mirrors and corrects them. Finally, it sends the correction to a wavefront control system (WFC).
- WFC handles the sampled signals from WFS and computes control commands for the mirror actuators of the deformable mirrors.

In order to correct the distortion, WFS uses some reference sources, natural guide stars (NGS), that is bright stars in the field of view, or laser guide stars (LGS) whose wavefront is known.

An advantage of the adaptive optics is the increase of the spatial resolution. Each pixel covers an angle of sky smaller than those in seeing-limited configuration. Thanks to the adaptive optics systems, the sky fluctuation for each resolution element is relatively modest, while it becomes significantly larger for seeing-limited imaging.

Figure 3.4: Operating principle of adaptive optics.^a

^a<https://www.eso.org/sci/meetings/2009/mad2009/presentations/LeLouarn.pdf>

Parameters to measure the accuracy of the wavefront correction by the adaptive optics system are the Strehl Ratio (SR) and Encircled Energy (Rodier 1999 [56]). The Strehl ratio is the ratio of the peak intensity of a measured point spread function (PSF) to the peak intensity of a perfect diffraction-limited PSF for the same optical system. The correction is perfect when $SR = 1$, which is just an ideal case. In all real cases $SR < 1$. The Encircled Energy (EE) is the amount of point image energy contained in a circle of given radius, centred at the intensity peak of the PSF. The accuracy is higher if the percentage of the EE contained in a given radius is higher.

3.5 DIT and NDIT

Unlike the optical case, where the exposure time can also cover a range of several minutes, in the infrared it must be reduced due to the sky fluctuation on time scale of a few minutes. In order to overcome the problem due to the sky fluctuation and to avoid saturating the detector due to long exposure time, it is necessary to split the single exposure in many sub-exposures (with time defined as Detector Integration Time, DIT) and to average them. The number of sub-parts of DIT is called NDIT, so the total integration time of a single frame is $DIT \times NDIT$. To have a good quality of frame, several images are averaged together.

Since the sky background varies on a time scale of 1-3 minutes, $NDIT \times DIT$ has not to exceed this limit ([44]).

3.6 Instruments

The images reduced in this thesis are taken with three instruments. Two are seeing-limited (SOFI and HAWK-I), while the other is adaptive optics assisted, MAD.

3.6.1 SOFI

SOFI (Son OF ISAAC, Infrared Spectrometer And Array Camera) is the infrared spectrograph and imaging camera, mounted on the Nasmyth A focus of the NTT (3.58m Ritchey-Chretien telescope located at La Silla in Chile).³ The data used for the present thesis have been collected in the following mode: Imaging with pixel scale (that is the portion of sky covered by one pixel) of $0.288 \text{ arcsec}^4/\text{pixel}$ in Large Field with FoV

³<http://www.eso.org/sci/facilities/lasilla/instruments/sofi.html>

⁴Arcsecond is a unit of angular measurement equal to $1/60$ of the arcminute, that is $1/60$ of one degree.

4.92'x4.92'.

Large field objective is affected by a distortion in a strip of about 200 pixels wide long the x-axis. This problem has been recently fixed.

The light from the tertiary mirror of the telescope enters the front window. After the window (see Fig. 3.5), there is a mask wheel, positioned at the telescope focus. This wheel contains all of the masks used for imaging and spectroscopy. Behind mask, there is a collimating lens, two filter wheels, a grism wheel, an objective wheel and then the detector (Rockwell Hg:Cd:Te 1024x1024 Hawaii array with 18.5 micron pixels). This information is written in the SOFI User's manual [44].

Figure 3.5: Optical layout SOFI [User's manual SOFI [44]].

The detector characteristics are (see ESO website [31]):

Array Format	Hawaii HgCdTe 1024x1024
Q.E.	65%
Pixel size	18.5 μ m
Gain	5.4e/ADU
RON	2.1 ADU
Bad pixels	About 1000
Non-Linearity	<1.5% over = to 10000 ADU
Dark current	<0.1 e/s

Table 3.1: Q.E. is quantum efficiency, the ability of the detector to absorb an incoming photon, described by ratio of incoming photons to those actually detected; Pixel size is the dimension of the pixel; Gain is the number of electrons collected in each pixel and converted in a digital number (ADU, analog to digital unit); RON is readout noise, that is the number of electrons per pixel into final signal after the reading of the device. It is linked to A/D conversion, which is not perfectly repeatable, and to introduction of spurious electrons by electronics themselves; Bad pixel, see sec 3.7 ; Non-Linearity represents the range in which the response of device is not longer a linear relation between the input value (charge) and the output value (digital number); Dark current is the current due to the electrons generated thermically (see ESO website [31]).

3.6.2 HAWK-I

HAWK-I (High Acuity Wide field K-band Imager) is a cryogenic wide-field imager installed at the VLT (Very Large Telescope) Nasmyth A focus of the Unit Telescope UT4 (8.2m, Ritchey-Chretien type, located at Paranal in Chile). HAWK-I has a FoV of 7.5'x7.5'. The detector is subdivided in four Rockwell HAWAII 2RG 2048x2048 pixels detectors (The pixel scale is 0.106 arcsec/pix). The four detectors are separated by gaps of about 15".

The detector characteristics are:⁵

Array Detector Parameter	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
Detector numbering	#66	#78	#79	#88
Gain [e ⁻ /ADU]	1.705	1.870	1.735	2.110

Q.E.	>80%
RON	5 e ⁻
Dark current [e ⁻ /s]	between 0.10 and 0.15
Non-Linearity	30000 ADU

⁵<http://www.eso.org/sci/facilities/paranal/instruments/hawki.html>

Figure 3.6: A detailed description of HAWK-I detectors. This image is taken from website of ESO [50].

HAWK-I is attached on the Nasmyth focus through an interface flange. The vacuum vessel contains the instrument and guarantees the mechanical stability among the all elements. It consists of a front part which extends to the interface flange, a central part which supports the cold mechanics and then final part which connects to the filters, detector and coolers. This assembly is cooled by cycle cooler which maintains the structure below 140K.

The light enters through the Entrance Window and reaches the four mirrors, then the filter wheels and, finally, the detector. The latter is attached to the back of the filter wheel unit and is cooled by other cycle cooler which maintains the detector and the filters at 80K.

Figure 3.7: Cut through HAWK-I for a mechanical overview. Blue: optical components; Black: cold assembly, filter wheels, detector; Green: radiation shield; Red: vessel structure, cryogenic components, electronic rack (Pirard et al. (2004) [54]).

3.6.3 MAD

MAD (Multi-conjugate Adaptive optics Demonstrator)⁶ is a prototype MCAO (Multi-Conjugate Adaptive Optics) system that had the goal to demonstrate on sky the feasibility of MCAO techniques for future implementations in E-ELT (European Extremely Large Telescope) and the 2nd Generation VLT Instruments (see Marchetti et al. (2003) [47], Marchetti et al. (2007) [48]). MAD was installed at the VLT Nasmyth A focus of UT3 (8.2m Ritchey-Chrétien telescope, located at Paranal in Chile) and was run in November 2007, January 2008 and August 2008; later it was decommissioned.

MAD is designed to perform atmospheric turbulence correction over wide Field of View (FoV) of 1 arcmin using Natural Guide Stars (NGS). This FoV is a "revolution" with respect to those of previous instruments with adaptive optics, which had a field of view of a few arcsec. The light coming from NGS is analysed through wavefront sensors, whose signal is used to reconstruct the atmospheric turbulence at different altitudes. The correction is applied by two deformable mirrors conjugated at different heights: one at the telescope pupil and the other at 8.5 km above the telescope aperture. The cycle continues until the wavefront error is reduced to a limit imposed by noise.

The optical layout is shown in Fig. 3.8. The light coming from telescope goes in MAD through a derotator which solves the image rotation caused by altazimuth⁷ configuration of the telescope. After a collimator, there are the two deformable mirrors and then a dichroic which transmits the IR light toward IR camera and reflects the visible light toward the WFS CCDs.

The infrared imaging camera installed on the MAD bench is CAMCAO (CAmera for Multi-Conjugate Adaptive Optics demonstrator) which consists of Hawaii2 2k x 2k IR detector with pixel scale of 0.028 arcsec/pixel.

MAD can use two different type of wavefront sensors (Marchetti et al. (2003) [47]):

- Multi Shack-Hartmann WFS for the Star Oriented MCAO. It consists of three movable SH WFS each one capable to look at any star present in the FoV. The SHWFS consists of a lens array and a CCD detector and measures the slope of wavefront.

⁶<http://www.eso.org/sci/facilities/develop/ao/sys/mad.html>

⁷A particular type of two-axis mount for which the telescope can move along horizontal and vertical directions.

Figure 3.8: Optical layout MAD [Marchetti (2003) [47]].

- Layer Oriented Multi-Pyramid WFS for the Layer Oriented MCAO, sensing 8 NGS. The Pyramid WFS consists of a pyramidal prim located at the focus and a detector. The prism divides the image in four beams which cross a lens that produces four images on a CCD. The wavefront errors produce a deflection of rays and different patterns on four images.

The CCD detectors consist of 5 WFS cameras (3 for SHWFS and 2 for LOWFS) based on the Marconi E2V CCD39 chip. This chip is 80x80 pixel, 24 μm size and four outputs.

Figure 3.9: Layout of two different WFSs..^a

^a<https://www.eso.org/sci/meetings/2009/mad2009/presentations/LeLouarn.pdf>

(a) SOFI M30 Image

(b) HAWK-I M30 Image divided in four chips

(c) MAD M30 Image

Figure 3.10: The different M30's images taken with three instruments in K_s band. It is noticed the different Field of View and pixel scale.

3.7 Instrumental Calibration

The goal of the instrumental calibration (called "pre-reduction") is to correct the instrumental artefacts and photometric variations for each raw image (see [44] and [39] for all information on the pre-reduction). The main effects to remove are the bad pixels, the bias connected to reading stage amplifiers, the dark originated from moving electrons, crosstalk, sky background, non-linear response of the pixels to incoming radiation and non-uniformity of the illumination of the detector (the last two are corrected thanks to the flat field correction).

A **bad pixel mask** is applied to solve the problem of bad pixels, which are:

- Dead pixels: they are permanently damaged pixels that does not receive any signal;
- Hot pixels: they are more sensitive pixels at the temperature and increase their luminosity during long exposure times;
- Frame pixels: they are the pixels masked by the edges at the focal plane field mask.

For example, in the user's manual SOFI [44] is described the use of two mask types. One has zero values at the bad pixels and one values at the good pixels. It has to multiply all raw data frame. The other mask has zero values at the good pixels and large negative values at the bad ones, and has to be added to the row frames.

The **crosstalk signals** occur when the pixel values in one amplifier affect the signal in other amplifiers. In this case, a bright source produces a "ghost" that affects all the lines where the source is and those in the other half of the detector. The crosstalk can be removed if the bright source is not saturated. Specific procedures are used to solve this problem [44].

The **bias** is not known a priori, but it is automatically removed for the IR arrays during the reading stage with the double correlated sampling technique.

The **dark** is not linear with time. This signal is composed of heat from the readout amplifier, dark current connected to electron-hole pairs and shading, a component which depends on the DIT and on incident flux. The dark frame is removed with the sky background, since the sky frames are taken under the same conditions and the same exposure time of scientific frames, in a time range close to them, and so sky and the scientific frames have the same dark frame pattern [44].

As already mentioned in the paragraph 3.2.1, the sky in the IR has a surface brightness and its background is not uniform across the field; this could cause some problems for the detection of faint sources or for photometry of extended sources. For this reason, it

is necessary to subtract from the source an estimate of the sky, so to make uniform each pixel to an only reference value. The method of **sky background reduction** depends on type of field ([44]): crowded or uncrowded one. In the case of uncrowded field, the sky observation is taken with the object observation itself. Several exposures of the field are made moving the telescope of a small amount (dithering technique) within the field. These images, collected by the dithering technique, are averaged among them, obtaining an only image for the sky. In infrared, high sky brightness limits the exposure time to 1-3 minutes, so it needs to make several observation of the field to obtain the sky level. If the field is crowded, the above technique cannot be used because in the field there are several objects. The telescope is moved toward "empty" sky outside the field to obtain sky frames (offset of the telescope). Minimum three sky frames are necessary, but in the practice 5-7 images are taken. The telescope is moved slightly between an observation and the successive one to remove array systematics (for example dead pixels) from image. Actually, the dithering technique is preferred with respect to the offset for some crowded and extended fields, because the time of offset is long. In addition, the offset can be used only for seeing-limited, because the movement of the telescope in AO assisted is difficult: this would involve the search of new guide stars, a new closed-loop etc.

Since each pixel has a different gain or quantum efficiency value than its neighbours, the goal of **flat field** is that to flatten the response for each pixel to the same wavelength [39]. Other sources of sensitivity variation can be dusts on the focal plane. The flat field is taken illuminating the detector with an uniform light source which can be the illuminated dome (dome flat, taken by difference between the exposure of an illuminated and an unilluminated dome panel, normalized to one), twilight (or dawn) sky or flat obtained from the observations themselves (the last two techniques are called sky flat). Each flat frame has to be obtained for each filter used for the observations, because the pixels have different responses to different wavelengths, and are usually taken each night of observation and for more images. These images are averaged together to form the final flat field. Later, the object frame is divided by the final one because the flat field is a correction of the gain, that is a multiplicative factor between number of counts and incoming photons per pixel.

It may happen that flat field does not describe completely the sensitivity variations of detector at the low frequency. For example, the dome flat contains a residual variation since the illumination of the panel is different from the illumination of the sky. In addition, the illumination of the screen can change with time due to the variation of the lamp. The problem is solved with an **illumination correction**: a bright star is observed in several positions along the array. Its intensities are fitted with a low order

polynomial, generated a surface which then is normalized to one. Finally, the flat field is multiplied by this surface to generate the corrected flat field ([44]).

The correct frame of the source will be:

$$Image = \frac{RawFrame - Sky}{normalized \langle Flat \rangle} \quad (3.2)$$

It is better to normalize the averaged flat field in order to not change the level of detected charge, because the flat field correction has to adjust the sensitivities of the pixels.

3.8 Photometric reduction

The "Photometry" term indicates the measure of the flux, or intensity, emitted by an astronomical object. The goal of photometry is to study stellar populations through the photometric information.

Two techniques exist (Howell (2006) [39], Stetson (1987) [67]):

- "Aperture photometry" is used in uncrowded field. It allows the measure of the flux adding the counts within a circular aperture of radius r centred on the central peak of star and subtracting the sky counts within an opportune annulus centred on the star itself. To estimate the sky background, its mean value \bar{B} inside the sky annulus is provided. Later, this value is subtracted from the total integrated photometric source signal S obtained from all pixels inside the star aperture. An estimate of the collected source intensity is $I = S - n_{pix}\bar{B}$, where n_{pix} is the total number of pixels contained within the area $A = \pi r^2$. To determine a source magnitude, the following standard equation is used: $Magnitude = -2.5 \log_{10}(I) + C$, where C is an appropriate constant and is determined in such a manner so that the calculated source magnitude is placed on a standard magnitude scale. A problem arising from the use of circular aperture on rectangular pixel grids is the presence of partial pixels. There are three possible choices: to not use partial pixels at all; to sum the values for every pixel within the source aperture; to make use of some computational weighting scheme that decides how to deal with the counts contained within each partial pixel in the source aperture.
- "PSF (Point Spread Function) photometry" is a fitting method that assumes as reasonable shape for count distribution of the stars an analytic or empirical function, so-called point spread function (an output function of detector that describes

a point source). For this reason, it can distinguish neighbours or partially overlapping stars with better precision, weighting the counts in each pixel. Therefore, PSF method is used in crowded field. In this way, the use of a circular aperture around the star is not necessary. Since in first approximation PSF is the same for all the stars on a given frame, the PSF is estimated from bright, isolated and non-saturated stars. Therefore, it is applied to other stars, taking in account their different position and different intensity of the peak.

There are two approaches to the derivation of model image profiles from observed ones: analytical and empirical one. The first employs a mathematical function to describe intensity as a function of two-dimensional distance from the centroid of a star. These may permit an imaged PSF to be matched well in radius and profile shape, allowing a simple integration to be performed to measure the flux. The analytic PSF can be integrated numerically over the area of each pixel in a stellar image. Typical analytic functions are Gaussian, Lorentzian, Moffat (a central truncated Gaussian overlapped with an exponential on the wings) and Penny (the sum of a Gaussian and a Lorentz function) [66]. The disadvantages are the long time necessary for numerical integrals and large number of parameters for description of formed images (for example, Penny has four free parameters: Half-Width Half-Maximum HWHM in x, HWHM in y, central value peak, amplitude function). The empirical approach uses bivariate interpolation to estimate intensity values at fractional-pixel positions within an observed stellar profile. The images of bright stars can be interpolated to a common grid, the resulting PSF can be numerically interpolated and scaled to match the observed data for each star. It is calculated more quickly than analytical PSF and avoids the problem of the free parameters. Its disadvantage is the interpolation of undersampled data.

In my thesis project, I made use of DAOPHOT/ALLFRAME (Stetson, 1987 [67]) and ALLFRAME (Stetson, 1994 [68]) software packages. These use both analytic and empirical function.

3.8.1 DAOPHOT and ALLSTAR

Before the running the DAOPHOT software, the user must know some input parameters, useful to identify the stellar sources. Some of the parameters are:

- Readout noise, gain and linearity range of detector;
- FWHM of stars;

- Two shape parameters, sharpness and roundness (defined below), within which a brightness enhancement is regarded a real star;
- A threshold, that is the level in standard deviation below which the objects are not considered stars.

DAOPHOT searches the candidate stars through the FIND task. It uses the given inputs to find the peaks of brightness, over the sky background threshold, and computes their centroids. FIND carries out a guess about which peaks could be the real stars, noise peaks, galaxies, cosmic rays or defects. It makes a convolution of image data with a lowered truncated Gaussian function whose FWHM is equal to the given input value, looks for the local maxima and excludes the the elongated stars in x or y , using the cutoffs in sharpness and roundness. Sharpness is defined as the ratio of the height of the bivariate delta-function to the height of the bivariate Gaussian function, while roundness is defined as the ratio of the difference between the heights of two 1-D Gaussians (computed by fitting the Gaussian function to sums of the data in x and y direction) and average of their heights (see [67]).

The successive step is the aperture photometry with PHOT task and it gives a first estimate of the magnitudes. The PICK task chooses the PSF stars and PSF task fits an analytic function (it can choose among Gaussian, Lorentzian, Moffat or Penny) to free parameters of respective functions (Half-Width Half-Maximum HWHM in x , HWHM in y , central value peak, amplitude function; only Penny has four free parameters, the other functions have at most three free parameters). It estimates the stellar profile and then computes empirically an look-up table, which represents the corrections from the best-fitting of the analytic function to the observed brightness values, interpolating the stellar profiles with a bivariate cubic interpolation. The PSF stars must be bright, unsaturated, isolated, with a good shape parameters and must uniformly sample the field of view of the CCD.

Finally, ALLSTAR (it is not a routine within DAOPHOT) is run. It applies simultaneously the PSFs found by DAOPHOT to all the stars of the frame and obtains the individual profiles for each star. In order to do this, it performs a linear least-square fit on each star and stops after several iterations, when the residuals by comparing the observed profile with the calculated one become lower than an established value. During every iteration, ALLSTAR subtracts all the stars from a copy of the image according to the best estimates of position and magnitude of each object. It computes the increments to the positions and magnitudes of the subtraction residuals around each position. The output of ALLSTAR is a catalogue with positions and instrumental magnitudes of each

star.

3.8.2 ALLFRAME

It is possible that double stars in some frames are recognized as a single star in other frames, this involves a large error of magnitudes and colours. In addition, it is needed to obtain a more accurate and a deeper photometry (that is to go up toward fainter magnitudes). For these reasons, a simultaneous photometry is made with ALLFRAME. If ALLSTAR works on a single image, ALLFRAME works simultaneously on all the stars in all the images available, independently of the filter, instrument and exposure time. If the PSFs are estimated for each frame and if the coordinate transformations of the images are found with respect to one reference image (by means of DAOMATCH/DAOMASTER [68]), it is possible to use the same list of stars to fit the same object simultaneously on all the frames. This list contains a star number larger than one of a single image, because it is obtained by the stack of all images by MONTAGE2 package [68]. This package takes into account of the coordinate transformations obtained thanks to DAOMATCH/DAOMASTER, for this reason a more photometric depth is reached. ALLFRAME performs a non-linear least-square fit using the PSF of the first frame, subtracts the objects from the first image and derives the corrections to star brightness values and to positions from flux residuals. Then, ALLFRAME performs the same procedure on the second frame and so on until the last image. The process is iterative. The benefit of ALLFRAME is the accuracy in the centroid determination, which ensures the precise estimates of the magnitudes. At the end of the process, ALLFRAME produces a catalogue with position and magnitude of every star in each frame and a star-subtracted image. The star-subtracted images can be stacked to search the faint sources not included in the previous star list and this sources can be added in it.

3.8.3 Photometric Calibration

Each instrument has its own response and each observation is carried out under different atmosphere conditions (Palmer & Davenhall (2001) [52]). For this reason, the measurements must be rescaled to a standard reference system, in order to compare the results with those obtained by other observers. This is the goal of the photometric calibration. The calibration is done through the observations of standard stars and the comparison between their instrumental magnitudes m_{instr} and those tabulated. Standard stars are stars whose the photometry is tabulated and is obtained with photometric standard systems (a specific set of filters, detector and telescope. See Appendix A).

Figure 3.11: This figure shows the allframe photometry is deeper than allstar one. In this case, the allframe and allstar photometry is made by two images collected with SOFI, in J and Ks band. The magnitudes are instrumental (not calibrated).

In order to rescale the instrumental magnitude to standard system, a typical calibration equation of the ground-based data is (Palmer & Davenhall (2001) [52]):

$$m_{cal} = m_{instr} + 2.5 \log T_{exp} + K_{ext}X + ZP + CT \quad (3.3)$$

where T_{exp} is the exposure time, whose correction is needed to normalize to 1s all the images, obtained possibly with different T_{exp} , CT is the colour term, K_{ext} is the extinction coefficient, $X = \sec z$ is airmass, where z is the zenithal angle, that is the angle measured between the vertical axis and the object at the time of observation (Lena (1988) [43]). Finally, ZP is zeropoint.

$K_{ext}X$ describes the atmospheric extinction. The instrumental magnitude is measured on the surface of the Earth and must be converted to the instrumental magnitude that would be observed above the atmosphere. This is necessary because the atmosphere absorbs the photons coming from the target and the amount of light absorbed depends on the angle of the star above the horizon; this changes night by night and depends on the place of observation. To resolve this problem, the atmospheric effect must be calculated. K_{ext} can be evaluated by observing of same standard stars at the different airmasses. It is the slope of linear relation between magnitude and airmass X . The correction for the atmospheric extinction is adopted in the case of standard stars not present in the

target field. In this case, it is necessary to obtain some frames of the region in which the standard stars are located.

The colour term and the zeropoint depend on the detector, the filter and the telescope, used to collect the data. They will have a slightly different response to the wavelength than the reference photometric standard system. Since some of the photons collected with an instrumental filter would fall into another filter of the standard system, it is usually to observe a standard star with two different filters, and to model the difference as a linear function of the color. The implicit assumption is that the differences between the standard and instrumental systems are not very large. The slope of this relation is the colour term, while the intercept is the zeropoint. For example, for the J and K bands:

$$J_{stand} - J_{instr} = CT(J_{instr} - K_{instr}) + ZP$$

Chapter 4

Data Reduction

In this chapter, I describe all the processing steps of the near-infrared (NIR) data, collected with SOFI, MAD and HAWK-I instruments. The photometric reduction was made through DAOPHOT/ALLSTAR and ALLFRAME software (see sec. 3.8). The obtained photometric catalogues were calibrated in the 2MASS¹ (Two Micron All-Sky Survey) photometric system. This system is based on the *J*, *H*, and *Ks* bands, whose effective wavelengths² are 1.25, 1.65 and 2.17 μm ,³ respectively. Finally, the cross-match of the NIR data with optical data found in the literature was performed.

4.1 The dataset

The dataset is composed by images collected with SOFI, MAD and HAWK-I instruments. The images collected with SOFI were taken in three nights of three different years from 2000 to 2007 in the *J* and *Ks* bands. The data were obtained with Large Field Imaging (see 3.6.1). The images were 28 and 16, in the *J* and *Ks*, respectively. The seeing⁴ conditions were good. The median of the seeing values of each image, according to the DIMM (Differential Image Motion Monitor) seeing monitor,⁵ was about 0.76 arcsec. The images collected with MAD were obtained during two observational runs in January 2008 and in August 2008. They were 50 and 50, in the *J* and *Ks*, respectively. The

¹2MASS is a near-infrared whole sky survey, created thanks to two 1.3 m telescopes in the northern and the southern hemisphere located at the Fred Lawrence Whipple Observatory in Arizona and at the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory in Chile, respectively.

² $\lambda_{eff} = \int F(\lambda)\lambda e(\lambda)d\lambda / \int F(\lambda)e(\lambda)d\lambda$, where $e(\lambda)$ is spectral efficiency (it describes the different sensibility of the measure system to different incoming wavelengths) and $F(\lambda)$ is the monochromatic flux.

³<http://www.ipac.caltech.edu/2mass/overview/about2mass.html>

⁴See definition in sec. 3.4.

⁵It is an optical telescope which measures wavefront slope differences.

median of the seeing values of each image taken with the DIMM seeing monitor was about 0.98 arcsec.

The images collected with HAWK-I were 38 and 121, in the J and Ks bands, respectively. The four chips that compose HAWK-I detector were reduced separately. I did not reduce some chip images because they contained too few stars of M30 to be useful, therefore the total number of reduced chip images was 138 J and 262 Ks . The seeing conditions were good for the nights of October 2014 and August 2015 with median value of ~ 0.76 arcsec, while for the nights of October 2013 and July 2015, they were slightly higher, with median of the order of ~ 1.10 arcsec for both.

The total exposure time for each instrument is, respectively in the J and Ks band: 1200s and 240s for SOFI, 1500s and 1500s for MAD, 76s and 242s for HAWK-I.

The MAD frames cover the centre of the cluster on a field of $\sim 2' \times 2'$, while the pointings of SOFI and HAWK-I are extended on a larger field: $\sim 15' \times 15'$ for HAWK-I, $\sim 6' \times 6'$ for SOFI (see Fig. 4.1).

Night	Band	Images number	Exposure time for each image (s)
2000, 2 July	J	8	4x36; 4x90
	Ks	16	15
2003, 5 September	J	19	30
2007, 29 July	J	1	126

Table 4.1: SOFI dataset. In 2000, there were four J -images with total exposure time of 36s and four J -images with total exposure time of 90s. Exposure time is DITxNDIT (see sec. 3.5).

Night	Band	Images number	Exposure time for each image (s)
2008, 12 August	Ks	50	30
2008, 15 August	J	50	30

Table 4.2: MAD dataset. Exposure time is DITxNDIT.

Night	Band	Images number	Exposure time for each image (s)
2013, 24 October	<i>J</i>	13	2
	<i>K_s</i>	63	2
2014, 12 October	<i>J</i>	15	2
2014, 13 October	<i>J</i>	10	2
2015, 20 July	<i>K_s</i>	38	2
2015, 28 August	<i>K_s</i>	20	2

Table 4.3: HAWKI dataset. Exposure time is DITxNDIT.

Figure 4.1: Pointings map: central square shows the portion of M30 covered by MAD stacked images; the intermediate square shows the portion covered by SOFI stacked images; the outer square shows the portion covered by HAWK-I stacked images.

4.2 SOFI Instrumental Calibration

The goal of the instrumental calibration (called the "pre-reduction") is to correct the instrumental artefacts and photometric variations for each raw image (see [44] and [39]). As mentioned in sec. 3.7, the main effects to remove are the bias, the dark current, the bad pixels, the sky background, the non-homogeneity of the gain of the pixels and the non-uniformity of the illumination of the detector. The first two can be removed during the reading stage of the array and with the sky background reduction, while the last two can be corrected through the flat field. In order to obtain the pre-reduced image, the sky background has to be subtracted from the raw image and the result has to be divided for the normalized flat field (see relation 3.2).

Since the MAD and HAWK-I images were delivered already pre-reduced, for this work I have pre-reduced SOFI images only, following the approach described in sec. 3.7, with standard IRAF⁶ routines. Below, I describe the steps followed to obtain the Flat Fields and the Sky frames.

According to the SOFI prescriptions (SOFI User's manual [44]), the **Flat Field** is obtained by multiplying the so-called "Special Flat" by the "Illumination Correction"⁷ and normalizing the result, as described in [44]. The Special Flat is created by exposing alternatively an illuminated and an unilluminated dome panel and is constructed from the difference of the two, normalized to one. The Illumination Correction removes the difference between the illumination pattern of the dome flat screen and the sky (see further details in sec. 3.7. See Fig. 4.3). The SOFI flat fields are extremely stable over a period of almost a year, therefore it is not necessary to take the flats every night (see Fig. 4.2).

Figure 4.2: Stability of the Special Flat images: photometric accuracy as a function of the flat field age [User's manual SOFI [44]].

After having applied the multiplicative Bad Pixel Mask to the raw images (it has zero values at the bad pixels and one values at the good pixels), as described in 3.7, I have

⁶Image Reduction and Analysis Facility <http://iraf.noao.edu/>

⁷The "Special Flat" and the "Illumination Correction" are available in the ESO Calibration Data Archive <http://www.eso.org/sci/facilities/lasilla/instruments/sofi/tools/FitsArchive.html>

Figure 4.3: The left upper panel is the Special Flat frame; the right upper panel is the Illumination Correction; the left lower panel is the Flat frame (the multiplication of first two); the right lower panel is the bad pixel mask.

subtracted the **Sky frames** from respective images. The Sky background subtraction is necessary to obtain a uniform background on the whole field of view of the scientific image. The atmospheric emission produces a spatially and temporally variable pattern that is necessary to subtract from the frame. The sky images have to be collected temporarily close to the scientific image through the dithering technique (see sec. 3.3) and with the same exposure time. The first condition is required from the time variability of the sky background; the second is satisfied to ensure a correct dark current correction of the scientific images. I have obtained the Sky frames averaging the sky images related to the respective scientific images. This average is necessary to remove some stars that can be present in the sky images.

The right panel of Fig. 4.4 shows some negative residuals present in the SOFI sky-subtracted image. This problem is due to the crowded field and the small number of the images averaged in order to obtain the Sky frame (only three frames were available for each scientific image). Because of that, some star residuals leave a higher background level at their position. At the time of the subtraction, these stars removes more flux than the local sky level in the object image, creating the "negative stars".

Finally, I have divided the sky-subtracted images by the normalized Flat Field obtaining the pre-reduced images.

Figure 4.4: In the left panel there is the raw image; in the right panel there is the pre-reduced image.

4.3 Photometry

After the pre-reduction, it is possible to proceed with the photometry of the images. Due to the crowding of the field, aperture photometry is not the best technique. Therefore, I have adopted a PSF fitting technique, by mean of the DAOPHOT/ALLSTAR/ALLFRAME suite of the software [67] [68] (see sec. 3.8 for further information).

Before proceeding with a DAOPHOT run, I have estimated the typical FWHM of the stars for each individual image with an IRAF routine, since it varies from image to image with the same instrument due to the seeing variations. This is an input parameter for DAOPHOT.

For each image, the software automatically selects a number (decided by the user) of bright and isolated stars, on which the PSF can be modelled. In this case, 30-35 PSF stars revealed to be a sufficient number. I have therefore used an IRAF routine to check the correct modelling of the PSF, by showing the difference (called "the residual") between the actual and the computed PSF profile. The stars with not satisfactorily residuals were rejected. This procedure was run iteratively, until only stars with good residuals were left.

I have applied the PSF model to all the bona-fide stars on the image, by means of the ALLSTAR [68] software. For each image, ALLSTAR produces a photometric catalogue, in which there are listed the stars along with their significant parameters (position, in-

Figure 4.5: The left panel is a zoom 2x of an original image of M30 collected with HAWK-I instrument in the J band. The right panel is a zoom 2x of the respective subtracted image via ALLSTAR. The latter shows a good subtraction of the stars from the original one and, therefore, a good fit of stellar profiles. The "black spots" on the subtract image are the residuals (i.e. the differences between the actual and the computed PSF profiles) of the stars that ALLSTAR was not able to subtract very well. These spots are due to the larger noise related to the counts in the brighter stellar profiles (the noise is proportional to \sqrt{N} with N counts number) and due to the saturated stars.

strumental magnitude, quality of the fit), and subtracts each catalogued star from the original image (see Fig. 4.5). ALLSTAR individual catalogues reflect the conditions of the individual images on which they are built. Therefore, they suffer of limitations due to the seeing and the sky background. Moreover, this occurrence makes difficult to compare the photometric catalogues based on different telescopes/instruments, or even with the same instrument, but at different times. For example, a bad seeing can blur stars in crowded regions, and these stars can be incorrectly fit as a single star. When comparing these measurements with those obtained on images with a better FWHM, the comparison can give the wrong numbers. For these reasons, it turns to be useful to stack all the available images, therefore gaining a very deep image. I have built a list of the bona-fide stars on the stack,⁸ and then I have performed a photometric run on all the available individual images thanks to ALLFRAME [68], giving as an input a single star list. This approach ensures that the individual photometric catalogues are homogeneous between them, and that the comparisons are meaningful. In order to produce the master star list, I have calculated the geometric transformations between the individual images, in order

⁸The list is found thanks to the DAOPHOT run.

Figure 4.6: Left panel shows the stack of all the SOFI and HAWK-I images. Right panel: stack of the MAD images. The brighter angles are due to the output readout amplifiers.

to put all the stars in same reference system. To this aim, I have aligned the individual ALLSTAR catalogues to a chosen ALLSTAR reference catalogue (usually referred to the image with the best seeing) by means of the DAOMATCH/DAOMASTER package [68]. I have used the obtained geometric transformations as an input to calculate the stacked image, by means of the MONTAGE2 software [68] (see Fig. 4.6). I have therefore searched bona-fide stars on the stack and have used the so-produced master star list with ALLFRAME, to perform PSF-photometry on all the available images, simultaneously. Finally, thanks to DAOMATCH/DAOMASTER, I have aligned all ALLFRAME catalogues to a chosen ALLFRAME reference catalogue and have obtained a unique one, where for each star the magnitudes in the J and Ks bands are shown. These magnitudes are the weighted mean of the instrumental magnitudes present in the ALLFRAME catalogue related to the same star.

I have made the MAD data photometry with ALLFRAME separately from that of the SOFI and HAWK-I data, obtaining two different catalogues, which I have called MAD and SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue. The reasons of this approach are discussed in the next section.

4.4 Photometric Calibration

The goal of the photometric calibration is to transform the instrumental magnitudes, as measured by the adopted software, into standard magnitudes, in order to properly compare the obtained measurements with those obtained by other observers (see sec. 3.8.3). Current data were calibrated in the 2MASS photometric system. SOFI and HAWKI data were calibrated using directly the 2MASS local standard stars (i.e. reference standard stars that are present in the field of view). Unfortunately, it was not possible to calibrate directly the MAD data using the 2MASS local standards. Indeed, the faintest stars of 2MASS are already saturated in the MAD images. In addition to that, the difference in spatial resolution between MAD and 2MASS (0.028 arcsec/pixel for MAD [47]; 1 arcsec/pixel⁹ for 2MASS) is larger: a source detected as unique in 2MASS could be detected as a double (or even multiple) source in MAD; the standards present in the field of MAD are probably blended in 2MASS. This makes impossible a direct calibration. For this reason, the MAD photometry was made separately from that of SOFI and HAWK-I and so the calibration: SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue was calibrated on 2MASS survey, while MAD one on the calibrated SOFI+HAWK-I, used as catalogue of standard stars.

In order to calibrate the SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue, it has been necessary to transform the physical xy coordinates of the stars in the WCS (world coordinate system) right ascension and declination coordinate, provided by the 2MASS survey.

To this aim, I have computed an astrometric solution for the catalogue produced by ALLFRAME, and then have cross-matched the coordinates of the individual stars in both the ALLFRAME and 2MASS catalogues. A single catalogue was therefore produced, containing for each star the the standard (2MASS) and the instrumental (SOFI+HAWK-I) magnitudes.

The general calibration equation, as shown in 3.8.3, is:

$$m_{std} = m_{instr} + 2.5 \log T_{exp} + K_{ext} X + ZP + CT$$

where m_{std} and m_{instr} are standard and instrumental magnitude, T_{exp} is the exposure time, CT is the colour term, K_{ext} is the extinction coefficient, $X = \sec z$ is airmass, where z is the zenithal angle, and ZP is zeropoint.¹⁰ However, since I have used local standards, it was not necessary to account for the airmass term (the local standards have,

⁹<http://www.ipac.caltech.edu/2mass/releases/allsky/>

¹⁰See definitions in the sec. 3.8.3).

by definition, the same airmass as the other target stars). Moreover, the normalization term is already contained in the zero-point difference. Therefore, the adopted equation is:

$$m_{std} - m_{instr} = a + b(J - Ks)$$

where m_{std} and m_{instr} denote standard and instrumental magnitudes in a given band respectively and coefficient b is the colour term, while coefficient a is the zeropoint.

In order to determine the accurate calibration parameters, it was necessary to remove the stars with large photometric error and with large sharpness in absolute value. The sharpness is an image quality diagnostic: stars with sharpness significantly greater than zero are probably galaxies or unrecognized doubles; stars with sharpness significantly less than zero are probably bad pixels or cosmic rays (User's Manual DAOPHOT II by Stetson [66]). Therefore, this latter cut was useful to efficiently reject spurious detections by plotting the sharpness as a function of the apparent magnitude. These two cuts are chosen according to the quality of the available data. A reasonable cut of sharpness is $|\text{sharp}| \leq 0.2$ (e.g. [21]), while a reasonable cut in photometric error is $\leq 0.02-0.03$ mag.

I have chosen to not select in 2MASS photometric error because I would keep only the brightest stars, which in my case were the red giants. In this case, the calibration equation would have been calculated on a very narrow range in colour, and a strong extrapolation would have been applied to calibrate all the other stars. Instead, I have selected the sharpness for $|\text{sharp}| \leq 0.2$.

I have made an additional star selection separately for each band. The stars within a 1σ of each distribution of the $J_{2m} - J_{instr}$ ¹¹ and $K_{2m} - K_{instr}$ ¹² was kept (see Fig. 4.7).

The calibration parameters are shown in Tab. 4.4. It was possible to neglect to colour term in the J band, while it was considered in the Ks band. As a matter of fact, the typical $J - Ks$ colour range covered in the CMD is of the order of 0.7 mag. Therefore, the colour term in the J band can be negligible, because it implies a maximum error of $b(J - Ks) = 0.004 \cdot 0.7 = 0.003$ mag, which is quite smaller than the photometric uncertainties of 0.02 mag. On the other hand, the colour term cannot be negligible in the Ks band, because $b(J - Ks) = -0.03 \cdot 0.7 = 0.021$ is of the same order of the photometric uncertainties.

In order to calibrate the MAD catalogue, it was necessary to transform preliminarily the coordinates of the stars in the MAD catalogue in the system of the SOFI+HAWK-I

¹¹ J_{2m} indicated the standard magnitudes of 2MASS and J_{instr} the instrumental magnitudes of the SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue.

¹² K_{2m} indicated the standard magnitudes of 2MASS and K_{instr} the instrumental magnitudes of the SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue.

Figure 4.7: They are the distributions of $J_{2m} - J_{instr}$ and $K_{2m} - K_{instr}$ on which a Gaussian is fitted. The Gaussians have $\mu = 2.212$, $\sigma = 0.037$ and $\mu = 2.464$, $\sigma = 0.047$, in the J and Ks band, respectively.

Figure 4.8: Fit of colour terms of the J -band (left panel) and of the Ks band (right panel) in the SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue. J_{instr} and K_{instr} denote the instrumental magnitudes, while J_{2m} and K_{2m} denote the standard magnitudes of 2MASS.

Band	Zeropoint	Colour Term	rms error
J	2.21	0.004	0.02
Ks	1.46	-0.03	0.02

Table 4.4: Calibration parameters for SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue for each band.

catalogue. From this, I have selected in sharpness $|\text{sharp}| \leq 0.2$ and in photometric error, keeping errors $\sigma(\text{mag}) \leq 0.03$, for both MAD and SOFI+HAWK-I measurements (see Fig. 4.10). I have performed an additional star selection separately for each band. I have kept only the stars within a 1σ of each distribution of the $J_{haw} - J_{mad}$ ¹³ and $K_{haw} - K_{mad}$ ¹⁴ (see Fig. 4.9).

Figure 4.9: They are the distribution of $J_{haw} - J_{mad}$ and $K_{haw} - K_{mad}$ on which a Gaussian is fitted. The Gaussians have $\mu = 2.646$, $\sigma = 0.090$ and $\mu = 1.969$, $\sigma = 0.096$, respectively.

The calibration equation was computed as already discussed and, in this case, the colour term was negligible both J and Ks measurements. For this reason, I have not taken into account it. Therefore, I have performed the calibration only on the zeropoint parameter (see Fig. 4.11).

¹³ J_{haw} indicates the standard magnitudes of SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue and J_{mad} the instrumental magnitudes of MAD.

¹⁴ K_{haw} indicates the standard magnitudes of SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue and K_{mad} the instrumental magnitudes of MAD.

Band	Zeropoint	rms error
J	2.65	0.035
Ks	1.97	0.030

Table 4.5: Calibration parameters for MAD catalogue.

Figure 4.10: Photometric error as a function of the instrumental magnitudes, in the MAD catalogue, in J and Ks bands, extended up to 0.3 mag. Two different sequences of the stars are present, due to a different signal to noise ratio. At fixed instrumental magnitude, the stars with lowest S/N are those with larger error, since they are stars collected in a fewer number of the images. The stars with a large photometric error present between 12 and 15 mag are noise spikes, detected by the software as stars. They can be removed from the catalogue thanks to the selection in sharpness.

Figure 4.11: The straight lines of the calibration for the MAD catalogue in J (upper panel) and Ks (lower panel) band.

4.5 NIR catalogues and Colour-Magnitude Diagrams

The catalogues obtained from the photometric calibration are written in the form shown below:

#	ID	x	y	Kinstr	sKinstr	Jinstr	sJinstr	chi	sharp	Kcal	Jcal
5000001		290.148	-892.615	16.955	0.1904	19.013	0.1899	0.7915	2.0680	18.926	21.667
5000002		-168.876	-892.510	16.696	0.1422	17.140	0.0653	0.6485	1.5795	18.667	19.794
5000003		975.820	-891.983	99.9999	9.9999	18.717	0.1855	0.6160	-5.9720	99.9999	21.371

These are the first rows of the MAD catalogue. **ID** is the star identification assigned from the DAOMASTER. **x** and **y** are the coordinates in pixel referred to the reference image given to DAOMATCH. **Kinstr** and **Jinstr** are the instrumental magnitudes, while **Kcal** and **Jcal** are the calibrated magnitudes. **sKinstr** and **sJinstr** are the respective photometric errors. **chi** and **sharp** are two image-peculiarity indices which can be used to identify a disturbed image. **sharp** is sharpness, already defined in the previous section. **chi** is the ratio of the observed pixel-to-pixel scatter in the fitting residuals to the expected scatter [66]. The value 99.9999 for **Kinstr** and **Kcal** and 9.9999 for **sKinstr** represent the lack of the photometric measure in the *Ks*-band for the star.

They have a different number of the stars: SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue contains about 26000 stars, while MAD catalogue contains about 17500 stars.

Finally, I obtained the colour-magnitude diagrams (Fig. 4.13), keeping only the stars of the catalogues with $|\text{sharp}| \leq 0.2$, a reasonable cut of sharpness¹⁵ used in the literature. I have not selected in photometric error, because this would cause the loss of the faintest stars. The diagrams show a photometry with an ample range in magnitude: about 7 mag for the SOFI-HAWK-I, 8 mag for the MAD catalogue.

The fainter stars for both catalogues have overestimated magnitudes. Indeed, DAOMASTER makes a weighted average of the magnitudes of the available measurements, excluding those with a photometric error higher than 0.3 mag. Therefore, given a symmetrical parent population, DAOMASTER keeps only the measurements under this limit. This has no effect on the brighter stars, but affects the faintest stars, which have low S/N ratio and therefore higher photometric error. Thus, average magnitudes are overestimated in the faint tail of the luminosity distribution. This is visible as an almost horizontal tail in the CMD (P. Stetson, private communication). In addition of that, up to 18 mag for

¹⁵The sharpness is an image quality diagnostic: stars with sharpness significantly greater than zero are probably galaxies or unrecognised doubles; stars with sharpness significantly less than zero are probably bad pixels or cosmic rays.

SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue and 18.5 mag for MAD catalogue, the stars become less and less, due to the lower signal to noise ratio and, therefore, not detected by software.

The shown CMDs have on the vertical axis always the band with the longer effective wavelength, since it is less sensitive to the reddening. Error bars in magnitude axis are the mean photometric errors per bin of magnitude, while in colour are the mean errors per band, at that magnitude level, summed in quadrature.

The obtained CMDs show all evolutionary sequences: main sequence, sub-giant branch, red giant branch, horizontal branch (these sequences are outlined in the Fig. 4.12, contained in the coloured boxes).

Figure 4.12: $(K_s, J - K_s)$ CMD, based on the SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue. The evolutionary sequences are shown within the coloured boxes.

The morphology of the evolutionary sequences in the infrared is different when compared with the optical one. In the infrared, the cool stars are brighter than the corresponding ones in the optical, while the hot stars are fainter. For this reason, the slope of the HB is steeper in the IR: the hot HB stars in the blue region emit mainly in the optical and UV radiation and therefore they are fainter in the IR. The same happens in the SGB, whose slope in the IR is steeper than in the optical. This affects the Turn-Off position determination. The Fig. 4.13 shows the CMDs based on SOFI+HAWK-I (upper panel) and MAD (lower panel) catalogues. The CMD of the MAD catalogue is deeper of about 0.5 mag than SOFI+HAWK-I one. The spread in colour of the MAD RGB is due to the non-linearity of the instrument (in the brighter RGB) and the PSF model no-optimized to measure the brighter stars in adaptive optics. Indeed, they are oversampled because of the small pixel scale ($0.028''/\text{pixel}$). Instead, the width of the main sequence and of the sub-giant branch in MAD CMD is similar to HAWK-I one.

Figure 4.13: $(K_s, J-K_s)$ CMDs, based on the SOFI+HAWK-I (upper panel) and MAD (lower panel) catalogues.

4.6 Optical-NIR catalogues and CM Diagrams

Using data collected with ground-based telescopes and HST (Hubble Space Telescope), I can couple the optical photometry with the NIR one obtained in this work. This allows us to study the stars in wavelength range from 4000 to 22000 Å. The extension of the catalogues can be made by cross-correlating the spatial coordinates for each star present both the optical and NIR catalogues via DAOMATCH/DAOMASTER. Also the stars with a single measurement (optical or NIR) can be contained in the extended catalogue. By the cross-match of the coordinates, a single catalogue is obtained, containing for each star the magnitudes corresponding to all available bands. This cross-match is made only between catalogues obtained with instruments having similar spatial resolution, because double stars, for example, in an image collected with a high resolution instrument can be recognize as a single star in a frame collected with a low resolution one.

The catalogues cross-matched with the NIR data are two: A. Sarajedini's and P. Stetson's catalogue. The first one is obtained thanks to the data collected with the channel WFC (Wide Field Channel) of the instrument ACS (Advanced Camera for Surveys)¹⁶ of HST in the *F606W* and *F814W* bands.¹⁷ The magnitudes *F606W* and *F814W* are rescaled to the ground-based *V* and *I* bands, respectively, according to the transformations provided by Sirianni et al. (2005) [64]. It contains about 73700 stars. The second catalogue is obtained thanks to the data collected with several ground-based telescopes in *B*, *V*, *I* bands and it is not available online. It contains about 19500 stars.

I have coupled the MAD-based photometry with the optical photometry collected with ACS, because these instruments have similar spatial resolution: 0.028"/pixel for MAD [47] and 0.05"/pixel for ACS@HST.¹⁸

Finally, I have cross-matched the SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue with the optical one provided by Stetson. Stetson's catalogue cannot be cross-matched with MAD one, since the first lacks the stars contained in the centre of M30 because of the crowding, while the second one contained only the stars in the centre.

I have called the NIR-optical catalogues: Sarajedni+MAD and Stetson+SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue, respectively. These catalogues show the identification number, coordinates *x* and *y*, calibrated magnitudes in the available bands.

¹⁶See Appendix D.

¹⁷Sarajedini's catalogue is published in http://www.astro.ufl.edu/~ata/public_hstgc/.

¹⁸<http://www.stsci.edu/hst/acs/documents/handbooks/current/toc.html>

I have obtained the colour-magnitude diagrams from the SARAJEDINI+MAD and STETSON+SOFI+HAWK-I catalogues. They have on the vertical axis always the band with the longer effective wavelength, since it is less sensitive to the reddening. The diagrams show a photometry with an ample range in magnitude: 12 mag for the Sarajedini's, 10 mag for the Stetson's catalogue. Error bars in magnitude axis are the mean photometric errors per bin of magnitude, while in colour are the mean errors per band, at that magnitude level, summed in quadrature.

Below, I show the CMDs in the optical and NIR-optical planes ($I, V - I$), ($V, B - V$), ($I, B - I$), ($B, B - Ks$), ($Ks, V - Ks$), ($I, I - J$), for both catalogues (where it is possible). The diagrams in the optical bands show a different morphology of the evolutionary sequences when compared with the NIR bands (see Fig. 4.13, 4.14). Regarding the HB and SGB, their stars have about the same brightness, so that these sequences are nearly horizontal in the optical CMDs, above all in the B band (see plane ($B, B - Ks$) in the Fig. 4.15). Indeed, the hot stars present in the blue edge of the HB and SGB emit mainly in optical and UV wavelengths and thus they appear brighter in the optical than in the IR, making the sequences almost horizontal. Instead, regarding the Tip of the RGB, it is fainter in the optical bands (above all in the V and B bands), because these stars are cool and emit mainly in the IR. Indeed, the RGB tip in the ($B, B - Ks$) plane is fainter of about 3 mag than in the Ks band (see Fig. 4.13 and the lower panel of Fig. 4.15). Otherwise, the Turn-Off is brighter in the optical, because the stars are hotter and emit in these wavelengths. Finally, thanks to the extension of the NIR catalogue up to B -band, it is possible to have more sensitivity to subtle differences in effective temperature. Large colour baseline, as $B - Ks$ or $V - Ks$, results in a clear separation among the HB, RGB and AGB.

Figure 4.14: $(I, V - I)$ CMDs, based on the Stetson's data (upper panel) and Sarajedini's data (lower panel). The CMD with the data from the space is deeper than the data from the ground-based. The Sarajedini's data photometry is more accurate in the fainter magnitudes than the Stetson's data photometry. This can be deduced from the error bars of the CMD in the upper panel larger than those of the CMD in the lower panel. The evolutionary sequences of the HB and SGB are less steep than those in the IR CMDs. In the lower panel can be seen the blue stragglers. They are stars brighter and hotter than TO, whose formation is due to mass transfer between binary companions and stellar mergers resulting from direct collisions between two stars. They are in the colour range 0.0-0.6 mag and in the magnitude range of 17-19 mag.

Figure 4.15: $(V, B - V)$, $(I, B - I)$ and $(B, B - Ks)$ CMDs, based on the Stetson+SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue. The diagrams show the different sensitivity to the effective temperature: the colour $B - I$ and above all $B - Ks$ are more sensitive to T_{eff} variation than the $B - V$ colour. Indeed, the extension in colour is about 1.2 mag in the $(V, B - V)$ plane, 2.5 mag in the $(I, B - I)$ plane and 4 mag in the $(B, B - Ks)$ plane. This is due to the larger difference in wavelength between two used bands in the $(I, B - I)$ and $(B, B - Ks)$ planes. The error bars are larger in the fainter magnitudes in the $(V, B - V)$ and $(I, B - I)$ planes. In the I band, the RGB Tip is brighter than that in the V and B bands. Indeed, the V and B bands are less sensitive for cooler stars, unlike the infrared and I bands.

Figure 4.16: $(K_s, V - K_s)$ CMDs, based on the Stetson+SOFI+HAWKI (upper left panel) and Sarajedini+MAD (upper right panel) catalogue. $(J, I - J)$ CMDs, based on the Stetson+SOFI+HAWKI (lower left panel) and Sarajedini+MAD (lower right panel) catalogue. These diagrams are in the NIR-optical planes. They have the same morphological features listed in the previous section for the infrared wavelengths, because the CMDs have the IR bands in the vertical axis. The upper panels show a wide range in colour due to the large difference in wavelength between the V and K_s bands, while the lower panels show a narrow range in colour, because the I and J bands are near in wavelength.

Chapter 5

Data Analysis

In this chapter, I show the comparison between colour-magnitude diagrams and theoretical predictions (isochrone and ZAHB). I have estimated qualitatively the distance modulus, the reddening and the age. Later, I have looked for the RGB bump both theoretically by the models and observationally by fitting of the peak along RGB of the 3-dimensional CMD. The analysis of its position reveals a disagreement between predictions and observations. Because the RGB bump location is affected by several uncertainties, I have used the ΔV_{HB}^{bump} parameter independent of the them.

5.1 Distance, Reddening and Age Determination

By comparing theory and observations, I have determined the clusters parameters, as the distance modulus and the reddening, and the age. Regarding to the theory, I have adopted the theoretical isochrones and ZAHBs from the Pisa Stellar Evolution Database (Dell’Omodarme et al. (2012) [25]). The theoretical models are transformed from the theoretical plane ($\log T_{eff}$, $\log L/L_{\odot}$) into the observational one using the bolometric corrections and T_{eff} -colour relations (see Appendix A). These transformations are based on the synthetic spectra by Allard et al. (2011) [3] for $T_{eff} < 10000$ K and Castelli & Kurucz (2003) [19] for $T_{eff} > 10000$ K. I have chosen the models with metallicity closest to estimated M30 one and with inputs: helium abundance $Y = 0.249$, metal content $Z = 0.0001$ ($[Fe/H] = -2.35$), α -enhancement $[\alpha/Fe] = +0.3$, mixing length parameter $\alpha_{MLT} = 1.90$. I have chosen $\alpha_{MLT} = 1.90$ because it is the best parameter that reproduces the RGB colour.

I have chosen to estimate the cluster parameters, distance and reddening, by over-

lapping the theoretical model ZAHB on the lower envelope of the observed HB. The procedure that I have used is that to shift simultaneously the ZAHB position in horizontal and vertical direction, until it has been placed to the lower bound of the observed HB star distribution. In order to apply this approach, it is necessary that the HB shape is neither too steep nor too flat, so that the parameter determination is easier. Indeed, the slope change of the HB morphology between the red and blue HB is useful to succeed the reddening estimate, because it determines the horizontal shift. While the no-steep HB morphology is useful to succeed the reddening estimate, because it determines the vertical shift.

It is necessary to evaluate the best plane where to estimate the parameters, because the HB morphology depends on the used bands (see Fig. 5.1). In the infrared bands, the slope of the HB is steeper and there is not the slope change between the red HB and the blue HB, necessary to estimate the reddening. Therefore the IR bands are not optimal for the distance modulus and the reddening estimate. Also in the I -band, the slope is steeper than the V and the B band. Instead, the HB is almost horizontal in the B -band and this affects the reddening estimate. For this reason, the V -band can be considered the best one in order to estimate the distance modulus and the reddening.

Because I had to estimate the age, I have chosen a plane with the narrow Turn-Off region. The best plane is: $(V, V - I)$ by Sarajedini's data.

First of all, I have overplotted the theoretical ZAHB on the observed HB. I have searched to overlap the ZAHB model on the stars of the blue HB, because the stars in the red HB are too spread. By shifting the ZAHB simultaneously in the vertical and the horizontal direction, until it has been placed to the lower envelope of the observed HB, I have found the apparent distance modulus (i.e. no-correct for the extinction). It is the difference between the apparent magnitudes of the lower HB level and the absolute magnitudes of theoretical ZAHB. I have determined reddening by the horizontal shift of the theoretical ZAHB. This shift in colour (in this case, $V - I$) is the colour excess $E(V - I) = A_V - A_I = A_V (1 - A_I/A_V)$ (see sec. 2.1), where the extinction A_I depends on A_V by the Cardelli law [7]:

$$A(\lambda)/A_V = a(\lambda^{-1}) + b(\lambda^{-1})/3.1$$

λ is the effective wavelength of the considered band and 3.1 is a factor of proportionality between the extinction coefficient A_V and the reddening $E(B - V)$, according to relation $A_V = 3.1E(B - V)$ [7]. $a(\lambda^{-1})$ and $b(\lambda^{-1})$ are for the IR bands and the optical ones,

Figure 5.1: These panels show the HB morphology in the available bands. Regarding to the J and the K_s bands, the HB is steeper and there is not the slope change between blue and red HB. For this reason, it is very difficult to estimate the parameters from these bands. Also HB slope in the I band is quite steeper than the V and B bands. Instead, the HB morphology is almost completely horizontal. For this reason, the V -band can be considered the best one in order to estimate the distance modulus and the reddening.^a

^aObviously, the HB morphology can vary changing the colour of the plane.

respectively [7]:

$$a(x) = 0.574x^{1.61}$$

$$b(x) = -0.527x^{1.61}$$

$$a(x) = 1+0.17699y-0.50447y^2-0.02427y^3+0.72085y^4+0.01979y^5-0.77530y^6+0.32999y^7$$

$$b(x) = 1.41338y+2.28305y^2+1.07233y^3-5.38434y^4-0.62252y^5+5.30260y^6-2.09002y^7$$

where $x = \lambda^{-1}$ and $y = (1 - x)$.

Therefore, the coefficients $a(\lambda^{-1})$ and $b(\lambda^{-1})$ are computed knowing the effective wavelength of I band. Hence, the horizontal shift $E(V - I)$ depends on the extinction A_V times a known constant, that is $c = (1 - A_I/A_V)$. Therefore, the reddening is $E(B - V) = cE(V - I)/3.1$. Subtracting A_V from the apparent distance modulus, I have estimated the absolute one: $\mu = (m - M)_V - A_V$. Finally, I have obtained the extinctions in the other bands according to the relation $A(\lambda) = 3.1E(B - V)(1 - A(\lambda)/A_V)$ (see Tab. 5.1).

Extinction coefficients	λ_{eff} (μm)	
$A_B/A_{V,Card.}$	1.348	0.436
$A_V/A_{V,Card.}$	1.016	0.545
$A_I/A_{V,Card.}$	0.590	0.789
$A_J/A_{V,Card.}$	0.288	1.25
$A_{Ks}/A_{V,Card.}$	0.117	2.17

Table 5.1: The table shows the extinction coefficients found using the Cardelli relations. They have been calculated again, since the values adopted by Cardelli et al. (1988) are based on the Johnson standard system, while my data are based on the Johnson-Cousins (Sarajedini's and Stetson's catalogues) and 2MASS (MAD and SOFI+HAWK-I catalogues) standard system. The effective wavelengths are taken from Bessell (2005) [6] (B , V , I) and <http://www.ipac.caltech.edu/2mass/overview/about2mass.html> (J , Ks).

The approach I am using to determine the cluster parameters does not provide an automatic estimate of the error budget. However, I can provide a quantitative estimate of errors affecting the determination of the different parameters. An uncertainty that can affect the distance modulus and the reddening is the mean photometric error at

the HB magnitude. Indeed, this involves a uncertainties on the ZAHB lower envelope position. It is $\sim \pm 0.01$ mag¹ for each bands, therefore it is $\sim \pm 0.014$ mag in colour (it is the add in quadrature of the mean photometric uncertainties on single band). They can be adopted as errors on the distance modulus and the reddening, but are certainly an underestimate of the error. Indeed, the error due to the shift procedure should take into account, but it is hardly evaluated. Moreover, the reddening and the distance modulus estimates depend strongly on the standard candle used to determine them. I have used as standard candle the ZAHB compared with the theoretical model. Therefore, important sources of error due to the model are the used chemical composition, input physics and model atmospheres (an example of the effect of the different model atmospheres is shown in Fig. 5.2). Changing these, the parameter estimates vary. Regarding to the uncertainty due to the input physics, I have found a value of $\Delta \log L_{HB} = \pm 0.045$ dex, that is $\sim \pm 0.1$ mag, estimated by Valle et al. (2013) [73]. It can be added in quadrature to $\sim \pm 0.01$ mag and becomes about $\sim \pm 0.1$ mag, error related to the distance modulus estimate. In first approximation, the error on the He and metal content can be negligible, because a He or metallicity increase (they are related thanks to $Y = Y_P + (\Delta Y/\Delta Z) Z$) implies opposite variations in the ZAHB luminosity.

Figure 5.2: It shows two Pisa ZAHB with the same reddening and distance modulus, but dissimilar transformations in the observational plane due to two different model atmospheres: Allard et al. (2011) [3] and Castelli & Kurucz (2003) [19]. The discrepancy is quite large at hotter temperature. This involves different reddening and distance modulus estimates.

Therefore, the adopted errors represent a lower limit on the true errors of the distance modulus and the reddening.

The absolute distance modulus and the reddening estimated through this method are: $\mu = 14.65 \pm 0.10$ mag and $E(B - V) = 0.054 \pm 0.014$ mag. The Fig. 5.3 show the

¹I have obtained the mean photometric error per bin of magnitude thanks to IDL procedure.

good agreement between model and data in each available band.

Figure 5.3: These panels show the agreement between theory and observations, adopting the distance modulus and the reddening estimates, in different planes. The first plane is the CMD in which the cluster parameters were determined.

Finally, I have estimated the age, overplotting on the observed CMD ($V, V - I$) a grid of isochrones in the range of $10.5 \div 14$ Gyr with the same metallicity and with a step of 0.5 Gyr, corrected for the reddening and the distance modulus (see Fig. 5.5). From the comparison of the isochrones with the TO region, I have estimated the age of M30 as 12 ± 1 Gyr. Indeed, this isochrone has the best accordance with the data at the SGB when compared with the isochrones of 12.5 and 11.5 Gyr (see Fig. 5.4). The error on the

age determination was just preliminary estimate of the error accounting for the range of the isochrones that provide a qualitative agreement with the observed stars (see Fig. 5.5). This error does not take into account the distance modulus and the reddening one.

Figure 5.4: CMD ($V, V - I$), based on the Sarajedini's data with $\mu = 14.65$ mag and $E(B - V) = 0.054$ mag, on which the isochrones of 11.5, 12, 12.5 Gyr are overplotted. The isochrone with the adopted reddening and distance modulus that shows the best accordance with observations is the isochrone of 12 Gyr. Indeed, it has the best agreement with the observed SGB when compared with the isochrones of 11.5 Gyr and 12.5 Gyr.

Figure 5.5: $(V, V - I)$ CMD, based on the Sarajedini's data. Superimposed isochrones of metallicity $Z=0.0001$, with ages between 10.5 and 14 Gyrs, $\mu = 14.65$ mag, $E(B - V) = 0.054$ mag.

Finally, I show the comparison between colour-magnitude diagrams and models. The isochrone is reasonably in agreement with the data. Possible disagreements between models and data can be due to the uncertainties on the calibration, on the bolometric corrections or on the reddening. In several cases, the isochrones do not succeed to fit the RGB branch very well, because the convection is still one of the main weakness in the stellar modelling. It is based on some approximations depending on a free parameter α_{MLT} which has to be calibrated. Indeed, the slope of the RGB is related to α_{MLT} , since the RGB morphology depends on the efficiency of the convection in the outer stellar layers. A change of the convection efficiency has a strong impact on the RGB effective temperature, and not on the RGB luminosity: if the mixing length (see the definition in sec. 2.3.1) increases, the temperature gradient decreases and in turn the effective temperatures increase along the RGB, causing the RGB to become hotter.

The description of the comparison between models and observations is outlined in more details for each CMDs below:

In Fig. 5.6, the comparison between theory and observations is not so good in the upper panel, above all for the horizontal branch. However, the accordance between theory and observations is reasonable within the calibration uncertainties (rms=0.02 mag). In the lower panel, the theoretical sequences are in agreement with the data, except for the bright RGB due to the convection treatment.

In Fig. 5.7, the theoretical models are in agreement with the observational data. They are in accordance with all evolutionary sequences, except the fainter RGB due to the convection treatment.

In Fig. 5.8, the models are in good agreement with the data in the $(I, B - I)$ plane when compared with ones in $(V, B - V)$ (see TO position, MS and SGB). This is due to the fact that the slope of the reddening vector is steeper in $(V, B - V)$ than in $(I, B - I)$.

In conclusion, in Fig. 5.9, the theoretical SGB is not in good agreement in the CMDs based on the Stetson+SOFI+HAWKI catalogue, but it may be caused by a variation in the adopted chemical composition. On the other hand, the RGB of the isochrone is good agreement with the data in all CMD, except in the $(J, V - J)$ based on the Sarajedini+MAD catalogue.

In Fig. 5.10, the models are in agreement with the data, except for the SGB of the $(Ks, I - Ks)$ CMD based on Stetson+SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue.

Figure 5.6: $(K_s, J - K_s)$ CMDs, based on the SOFI+HAWK-I (upper panel) and MAD (lower panel) catalogues. ZAHB and isochrone have metallicity $Z=0.0001$, with $\mu = 14.65$ mag, $E(B-V)=0.054$ mag, Age=12 Gyr.

Figure 5.7: $(I, V - I)$ CMDs, based on the Stetson's data (upper panel) and Sarajedini's data (lower panel). ZAHB and isochrone have metallicity $Z=0.0001$, with $\mu = 14.65$ mag, $E(B-V)=0.054$ mag, Age=12 Gyr.

Figure 5.8: $(V, B - V)$ and $(I, B - I)$ CMDs, based on the Stetson+SOFI+HAWKI catalogue. ZAHB and isochrone have metallicity $Z=0.0001$, with $\mu = 14.65$ mag, $E(B-V)=0.054$ mag, Age=12 Gyr.

Figure 5.9: $(J, V - J)$ CMDs, based on the Stetson+SOFI+HAWKI (upper left panel) Sarajedini+MAD (upper right panel) catalogue. $(Ks, V - Ks)$ CMDs, based on the Stetson+SOFI+HAWKI (lower left panel) and Sarajedini+MAD (lower right panel) catalogue. ZAHB and isochrone have metallicity $Z=0.0001$, with $\mu = 14.65$ mag, $E(B-V)=0.054$ mag, Age=12 Gyr.

Figure 5.10: $(K_s, I - K_s)$ CMDs, based on the Stetson+SOFI+HAWK-I (upper panel) and Sarajedini+MAD (lower panel) catalogue. ZAHB and isochrone have metallicity $Z=0.0001$, with $\mu = 14.65$ mag, $E(B-V)=0.054$ mag, Age=12 Gyr.

5.2 Comparison with the literature

In this section, I compare the distance modulus, the reddening and the age estimated in this thesis with the latest values found in the literature. It is possible to find the oldest estimates in the tables in Kains et al. (2013) [41].

Distance

The most recent estimates of the M30 distance are shown in the Table 5.2. They were determined with different methods, described in the sec. 2.2:

- Kains et al. (2013) [41] estimated the distance using as standard candles the RR Lyrae stars (see sec. 2.2). They determined the mean apparent magnitude in V band by the parameter A_0 (amplitude of the 0th harmonic) of the Fourier decomposition to the light curves of four RR Lyrae of type ab (RR0) and three RR Lyrae of type c (RR1). The ab type variables pulsate in the fundamental mode, while the c type variables in the first overtone mode. The absolute V magnitude was obtained by the empirical relation between the period of RR Lyrae and the Fourier coefficients. Therefore, after having removed the extinction, the distance modulus is the difference between the absolute and the apparent magnitude.
- Dotter et al. (2010) [30] used as initial estimate the distance modulus taken from Harris (1996) [38] catalogue (2003 revision) and on this base they adjusted the value to improve the fit of the theoretical models to the level of the HB.
- Carretta et al. (2000) [10] used the method of the MS fitting. They compared the lower MS of M30 with an empirical template MS obtained by the parallaxes of subdwarfs (underluminous stars lied below the MS) observed by the Hipparcos satellite, with the corrected metallicity for the difference in $[Fe/H]$ between the cluster and the subdwarfs.

The distance modulus of 14.65 ± 0.10 mag is in agreement with that of Kains et al. (2013) and Dotter et al. (2010). The latter estimated the distance modulus with a similar approach to that used in this project. They used independent models, but in agreement to the isochrones and the ZAHBs from the Pisa Stellar Evolution Database. The value adopted by Carretta et al. (2000) is different, not only from 14.65 ± 0.10 mag, but also from other estimates. The disagreement might be due to the strong sensitivity of the subdwarf fitting method to the metal abundance [10].

Reference	Distance modulus (mag)	Distance (kpc)	Method
Kains et al.(2013)	14.60 ± 0.05	8.32 ± 0.20	RR0
Kains et al.(2013)	14.54 ± 0.05	8.10 ± 0.20	RR1
Dotter et al.(2010)	14.72 ± 0.05	–	CMD analysis
Carretta et al.(2000)	14.88 ± 0.05	9.46 ± 0.22	MS fitting

Table 5.2: Absolute distance modulus and distance estimates for M30 in the literature. The value 14.72 mag is taken from the paper Cohen et al. (2015) [21]: they show the absolute distance modulus obtained by the estimated apparent value of 14.82 mag from Dotter et al.(2010) [30].

Reddening

In the literature, several authors have estimated the reddening $E(B - V)$ (see sec. 2.1) of M30 since the 1970s, ranging from 0.01 to 0.12 mag. Therefore, it is very difficult to find a value in agreement with the most of the estimates in the literature. The latest values of reddening are shown in the Table 5.3:

- $E(B - V)$ adopted from VandenBerg et al. (2013) [76] was obtained by the Schlegel et al. (1998) [62] dust maps. The maps can be used, in conjunction with a spectral template of the background, to derive the dust temperature and opacity, and hence, extinction, along the line of sight.
- Schafly & Finkbeiner (2011) [61] provided new estimates of Galactic dust extinction from an analysis of the Sloan Digital Sky Survey. They re-calibrated Schlegel et al. (1998) results using their values as a starting point.
- Reddening adopted from Kains et al. (2013) [41] is $E(B - V) = 0.03 \pm 0.01$ mag. The used method was not specified in their paper.
- Dotter et al. (2010) [30] obtained $E(B - V)$ from the Harris (1996) [38] catalogue (2003 revision), varying it until the fit to the main sequence and the RGB obtained was acceptable.

My reddening estimate $E(B - V) = 0.054 \pm 0.014$ mag is in agreement with all values shown in the table. Dotter et al. (2010) estimated the reddening with a similar method to that used in this project. They used independent models, but in agreement to the isochrones and the ZAHBs from the Pisa Stellar Evolution Database.

Reference	Reddening $E(B - V)$ (mag)
VandenBerg et al. (2013)	0.051 ± 0.002
Schafly & Finkbeiner (2011)	0.044 ± 0.002
Kains et al. (2013)	0.03 ± 0.01
Dotter et al. (2010)	0.054

Table 5.3: Reddening estimates for M30 in the literature. The value using by Dotter et al. (2010) is taken from Cohen et al. (2015) because they shown the $E(B - V)$, while Dotter et al. (2010) the $E(F606W - F814W)$, where $F606W$ and $F814W$ are the filters of ACS.

Age

The latest studies assign an age to M30 ranging from 12 to 13.25 Gyr. The ages found by Kains et al. (2013) [41], VandenBerg et al. (2013) [76], Dotter et al. (2010) [30] and Carretta et al. (2000) [10] through the methods discussed in sec. 2.3, are shown in the Table 5.4. The used stellar models are: Vandenberg & Clem (2003) [74] by Kains et al. (2013), Victoria-Regina [75] by VandenBerg et al. (2013), Dartmouth [29] by Dotter et al. (2010), Straniero et al. (1997) [69] by Carretta et al. (2004). [74] and [75] do not include the diffusion, instead [29] and [69] yes. They adopt the diffusion by Thoul et al. (1994) [70], also used by the stellar models of the Pisa Stellar Evolution Database. The isochrones with diffusion have the Turn-Off fainter than the isochrones without it. Indeed, the diffusion takes the He and metals towards the centre of the star, increasing the molecular weight. In this way, the star leave earlier the Main Sequence. For this reason, the cluster has to be fitted with a younger isochrone.

Reference	Age [Gyr]	Method
VandenBerg et al. (2013)	13.00 ± 0.25	Mean of values based on ΔV_{TO}^{HB} and $\Delta H_{TO,RGB}$
Kains et al. (2013)	13 ± 1	CMD isochrone fitting
Dotter et al. (2010)	13.25 ± 1.00	CMD isochrone fitting
Carretta et al. (2000)	12.3	TO luminosity

Table 5.4: Age estimates for M30 in the literature.

The age estimate 12 ± 1 Gyr in this thesis is in good agreement with all references shown in the Tab. 5.4.

5.3 Luminosity of the RGB bump

In this thesis, I have focused on an evolutionary feature along the RGB, that is the RGB bump, and on the strong dependence of its location on any structural and/or physical parameter which affects the size of the convective envelope.

5.3.1 Introduction

Globular clusters possess several evolutionary features which are recognisable from the CMD and the luminosity function (that is, the star number counts as a function of the magnitude). One of them is the RGB bump, a feature recognisable from a clustering of stars along the RGB, that shows up as a peak in the luminosity function, at a magnitude level which depends mainly on the metallicity at fixed age.

The RGB stars have a He core, a H-burning shell and a convective envelope (see Appendix B). The convection present in the stellar envelope penetrates deeper during the stellar evolution along the RGB. The lower border of the convective envelope reaches regions in which the hydrogen was burnt partially in the main sequence phase and therefore enriched in He, C and N.² The convection carries the superficial chemical elements in the inner layers and He, C, N in the surface. The phase in which the convection reaches its maximum penetration is called the first dredge up. This involves a variation in the chemical composition and above all a H abundance discontinuity in these layers when compared with the inner layers. When the H burning shell reaches the H abundance discontinuity created by the penetration of the convective envelope, there is a temporary drop of stellar luminosity. This happens because the variation in the chemical composition affects the efficiency of the H burning shell. The increase of H abundance causes a decrease of the mean molecular weight μ and therefore a decrease of the luminosity, since the contribution to the luminosity given from H-shell is $L_H \propto \mu^7$ (Salaris & Cassisi (2005) [59]). Then, it grows monotonically with increasing He core mass M_c^{He} , since $L \propto M_c^{He}$ [59]. The stars cross the same luminosity range three times, causing an overdensity of stars in the RGB.

The RGB bump luminosity depends on the metallicity, the mixing length and the

²C and N are elements of the CNO-cycle, H-burning reaction channel alternative to pp-chain. The CNO cycle is the combination of two independent cycles: the CN cycle and the NO one. C, N and O act as catalysts and are both produced and destroyed during these cycles, dominant in the massive stars. The CNO-cycle is not totally inactive in the low massive stars. For this reason, elements as C and N are carried in the surface. Instead, the O abundance does not vary because the NO-bicycle is not active at those temperatures.

Figure 5.11: Zoom of the RGB Bump on the Pisa isochrone of 12 Gyr in the theoretical plane.

age. An increase of the convection efficiency, that is an increase in the mixing length, decreases the extension of the convection and therefore the bump luminosity increases (Salaris & Cassisi (2005) [59]). A decrease in the metal content abundance and/or in the age causes an increase in the bump luminosity, since the location of the chemical discontinuity is shallower due to the lower opacity. Therefore, the number of the stars decrease in the RGB bump, because the evolution is faster in the brighter part of the RGB [14]. For this reason, the identification of the RGB bump is difficult for metal-poor clusters (Di Cecco et al. (2010) [26]). In addition, one of the advantages in the identifying of the RGB bump in globular clusters is that to constrain the metal abundance, if the distance modulus and the age are known [26].

5.3.2 The ΔV_{HB}^{bump} parameter

In order to estimate the bump position, the observational uncertainties which affect the bump luminosity must be taken into account. They are the distance and the reddening. In order to avoid these uncertainties, Fusi Pecci et al. (1990) [33] suggest to use a new parameter, $\Delta V_{HB}^{bump} = V_{bump} - V_{HB}$, where V_{bump} is the apparent visual magnitude of the bump and V_{HB} is the apparent visual magnitude of the HB at the luminosity level of RR Lyrae (definition in 1.3). This parameter can be estimated theoretically from the models or observationally from the data in order to compare predictions and observations. By the comparison, it is possible to study discordances between the observed RGB bump position and the predicted one, not due to uncertainties arising of the calibration of observational data. Di Cecco et al. (2010) [26] find that the observed ΔV_{HB}^{bump} values are larger than predicted ones, in particular for metal-poor globular clusters: the dis-

crepancy is about 0.4 mag (see Fig. ??). The cause of this difference between theory and observations is still investigated, probably related to the mixing length of the convection in the stellar envelope of the RGB stars or the chosen metallicity scale. Di Cecco et al. (2010) [26] adopts models that include either α - and CNO-enhancement or helium enhancement and note that they do not alleviate the discrepancy.

The parameter was estimated for several clusters by Fusi Pecci et al. (1990) [33], Cassisi & Salaris (1997) [15], Riello et al. (2003) [55], Di Cecco et al. (2010) [26].

Therefore, in order to avoid uncertainties on the distance modulus and the reddening, I have estimated the ΔV_{HB}^{bump} parameter, rather than only the RGB bump position. Then, I have also determined the theoretical parameter to verify if the discrepancy between models and observations on the RGB bump position is found in M30. In order to compute the ΔV_{HB}^{bump} parameter, it is necessary to estimate the bump position and the magnitude of the HB level. I have obtained them both observationally from the data and theoretically from the models. Regarding the observational estimates, the magnitudes are apparent, while, regarding the theoretical estimates, they are absolute. In the next paragraphs, the identification of the RGB bump and of the HB magnitude level is shown.

RGB Bump identification

In metal-poor Globular Clusters as M30, the RGB bump is hardly observable for the reason shown in 5.3.1: the bump luminosity is brighter for low-metallicity, moving in a region where the evolutionary lifetime is quick and the star number is small. It has only been detected in a few metal poor GGCs (Di Cecco et al. (2010) [26], Valenti et al. (2004) [72]). The common technique to detect the RGB bump is by means of the luminosity function of the RGB.

In order to identify the RGB bump, the near-IR spectral domain offers several advantages, being the most sensitive to low temperature (RGB stars are cool). Moreover, the background contamination due to MS stars is much less severe. This allow us to properly characterize the RGB stars in the innermost core region of stellar clusters affected by crowding. In addition, in the IR range the reddening is much lower than the optical one (Valenti et al. (2004) [72]). For this reason and because the stars at the expected bump magnitudes are saturated in the SOFI+HAWK-I and the MAD catalogues, I have used the near-IR 2MASS catalogue. Because it contains several field stars in addition to the cluster stars (this catalogue is extended on a large field $\sim 40' \times 40'$), I have removed them from the catalogue, before proceeding with the luminosity function. Since the measure-

ments have been available at least in two bands, it is possible to make a cut in colour, removing all star bluer and redder than the RGB position of M30 (see Fig. 5.12). Its position has been identified overplotting the CMDs of the SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue (less contaminated by the field stars) on that of 2MASS. I have kept only 2MASS stars along the RGB location of the SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue (blue dots in Fig. 5.12).

As a result of the stars selection, I have made the histogram of their magnitudes for

Figure 5.12: Overplot of the 2MASS stars (red+blue dots) on the CMD of the SOFI+HAWKI catalogue (grey dots). The blue dots are the selected 2MASS stars. The larger number of the field stars in 2MASS when compared to the SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue is due to the different extension of the covered field: the first about 40'x40' and the second one about 15'x15'.

available band. I show the histogram in Ks -band in a range of 11÷13 mag with bin size of 0.09 mag in the Fig. 5.13. The bin with more counts indicates the RGB bump magnitude.

Since the previous method depends on the bin sizes and on the chosen maximum and the minimum magnitude, an accurate way to search the RGB bump is the following (see the Fig. 5.14: graphics performed by G. Bono and his collaborators). Each red giant star is represented by a Gaussian function with the height equal to the star magnitude and with σ equal to the average between the photometric error in magnitude and that in colour. Later, they are summed in magnitude and in colour. The graphics in the Fig. 5.14 represent a three-dimensional CMD: the vertical axis is the counts density at a given position in the CMD (called luminosity function index), the ordinate is the magnitude and the abscissa is the colour. The RGB bump location is found by fitting the peak of the CMD with a Gaussian and its mean value is taken as the RGB bump magnitude. Finding the RGB bump magnitude in a band and knowing the colour, it is possible to identify the bump in the other filter. In order to find the RGB bump in the remaining

bands, 2MASS has been cross-matched with the other catalogues. The uncertainties on the measurement of its position have been obtained adding in quadrature the photometric errors of the stars present in a range of 0.5 mag around the bump magnitude. The values obtained by fitting of the bump peak are shown in the second column of the Tab. 5.5.

Regarding to the theoretical RGB bump, I have found its position on the isochrone of 12 Gyr by the difference between the maximum and minimum value in the luminosity variation range in the theoretical plane (see Fig. 5.11). Knowing the bump luminosity value, it was possible to identify the respective values in absolute magnitude for each band. An accurate determination of the uncertainties on the theoretical values, depending on the metallicity, the helium content, the mixing length, the opacity, the input physics and the diffusion, is difficult. I show the overall error on the ΔV_{HB}^{bump} parameter, sum of uncertainties on the bump and ZAHB luminosity, in the last paragraph of this chapter. The values obtained from the isochrones are outlined in the third column of the Tab. 5.5.

Figure 5.13: The histogram of selected 2MASS stars in bin of magnitudes in Ks band. The RGB bump is indicated by a red arrow.

Band	Observed Bump (mag)	Theoretical Bump (mag)
B	15.52 ± 0.05	0.20
V	14.70 ± 0.04	-0.55
I	13.68 ± 0.04	-1.52
J	12.97 ± 0.01	-2.18
Ks	12.38 ± 0.01	-2.78

Table 5.5: The second column shows the observed magnitudes of M30 RGB bump. The third column shows the theoretical absolute magnitudes, predicted from the isochrone of 12 Gyr.

Figure 5.14: The graphics are the three-dimensional CMDs in $(J, J - K_s)$ formed by the sum of all gaussian profiles of the 2MASS stars. The first and the second graphic are obtained considering all 2MASS stars, while the third one is obtained only from selected 2MASS stars. The second and third panel are three-dimensional CMDs seen in projection in the luminosity function index- K s magnitude plane. The RGB bump is indicated by a red arrow. The peaks up to 13 mag are due to the longer lifetime of the stars in the lower RGB. The more smoothed peaks down to 12 mag are due to the field stars.^a

^aGraphics performed by G. Bono and his collaborators.

HB level identification

The HB level identification can be performed at the RR Lyrae (RRL) level. The HB magnitude determination is possible only in the optical bands, because the HB at this

level is quite horizontal. It is not true in the infrared bands due to the steeper HB slope, because stars at the hotter temperature emit the radiation more in the ultraviolet and less in the infrared (the Fig. 5.15 shows the different slope in the B , V , I , J , Ks bands). I have chosen to identify the observed HB level from the mean value of the RRL mean magnitudes, rescaled to ZAHB level, and the theoretical one from the value in magnitude corresponding to the coolest point of the ZAHB. Below, I show the HB magnitude determination in two cases.

The observed HB level can be identified at the RRL region, where the HB is almost horizontal, as the average of the magnitudes of the RR Lyrae.

For this reason, it was necessary to find them in the available catalogues. Therefore, I have used a complete list of the catalogued RRL in M30 and have searched them cross-correlating their spatial coordinates with those of my catalogue. A list of RRL present in M30 is shown in Kains et al. (2013) [41] and Clement catalogue (2001) updated in September 2014.³ The RRL coordinates found in the Stetson+SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue are shown in the Tab. 5.6.

Because I have not performed the light curves for RRL in order to obtain the mean magnitudes, I have used the RRL mean magnitudes found by P. Stetson in his catalogue (private communication). The period, mean magnitudes and amplitudes of the light curves are shown in the Tab. 5.7.

ID	RA	DEC	Type
V1	325.10095	-23.19631	RR <i>ab</i>
V3	325.06263	-23.19114	RR <i>ab</i>
V14	325.08788	-23.19194	RR <i>c</i>
V16	325.10334	-23.19694	RR <i>c</i>

Table 5.6: RR Lyrae in M30 found in the Stetson’s optical catalogue. ID is the identification number. RA and DEC are the right ascension and the declination in WCS system. RR*ab* and RR*c* indicate the type of the RR Lyrae (for definition see sec. 5.2).

Regarding the observed HB level, I have determined it as the mean value of the mean magnitudes of the RR Lyrae. Unfortunately, the number of the M30 RRL is very small and affects the obtained average.

Their errors are the mean photometric errors per bin of magnitude, corresponding to the

³<http://www.astro.utoronto.ca/~cclement/cat/C2137m234>

Figure 5.15: ZAHB on the SOFI+HAWK-I data (upper panel) and Stetson's one (lower panel). The ZAHB slope at the RRL level in the infrared is steeper than that in the optical bands.

ID	P	B	V	I	A_B	A_V	A_I
V1	0.744	15.41	15.06	14.52	1.13	0.86	0.60
V3	0.696	15.45	15.08	14.55	1.16	0.92	0.64
V14	0.352	15.38	15.13	14.75	0.56	0.43	0.35
V16	0.325	15.42	15.17	14.82	0.30	0.20	0.08

Table 5.7: ID is the identification of RRL. P is the variability period. B , V , I are the mean magnitudes and A_B , A_V , A_I are the amplitudes of the light curves.

Figure 5.16: RR Lyrae in M30, plotted in the CMD (V , $B - V$).

magnitude level of the respective RRL. The values are shown in Tab. 5.10.

Band	Observed HB level (mag)	$\Delta m_{HB,oss}^{bump}$ (mag)
B	15.42 ± 0.01	0.10 ± 0.11
V	15.11 ± 0.01	-0.41 ± 0.11
I	14.66 ± 0.01	-0.98 ± 0.11

Table 5.8: the second column displays the mean RRL magnitudes in the optical bands. They are considered the observed HB levels in the B , V , I bands. The last column is the observed Δm_{HB}^{bump} , the difference between the observed RGB bump and the values in the second column.

Mean RRL magnitude does not represent the value of the ZAHB luminosity, to which has to be corrected in order to compare the observed parameter with the theoretical one (calculated as difference between the theoretical RGB bump and the ZAHB value at the

RRL region). The ZAHB corresponds to the lower envelope of the observed HB stars distribution, while the RRL are evolved stars and, for this reason, they do not populate the ZAHB model (see Fig. 5.17). The stars in the red part of HB of M30, included the

Figure 5.17: CMD ($V, V - I$), based on the Stetson data, with $\mu = 14.65$ mag and $E(B - V) = 0.054$ mag. It shows that the ZAHB does not reach the RRL position.

RRL, can be evolved stars coming from the blue HB region. In order to verify this, it is possible to compare observations and theory and to check if the stars are in the evolved HB phase called "off-ZAHB". This approach is based on the HB morphology analysis and does not take into account the synthetic CMD. It is a theoretical diagram that shows the stellar distribution along the evolutionary tracks and isochrones, assuming a given initial mass distribution and observed uncertainties. It provides information regarding to the evolutionary times of stars and their position on the CMD.

First of all, it is necessary to verify if the stars identified as RRL are in the strip delimited by the ZAHB and the end of the core He burning locus, called "end He" in the showed plots. The Fig. 5.18 shows that the RRL are fully within the strip and, therefore, are HB stars. Moreover, they are stars that have overtaken the loci at the 50% and 80% of the stellar lifetime in the HB, characterized by two curves⁴ almost parallel to the ZAHB, but brighter (see Fig. 5.18). Therefore, it is plausible to think that they are not ZAHB stars and, for this reason, the theoretical ZAHB cannot cover the RRL region. Another test to confirm that the RRL are evolved stars is to shift the ZAHB up to the RRL mean magnitude level (thus changing the distance modulus) and to verify if the theoretical ZAHB and the observed HB are still in good agreement. The third panel of the Fig.

⁴I have obtained these curves identifying on each theoretical track the temperature and the luminosity of the star at 50% and 80% of its lifetime between the beginning of the He-burning and the depletion of He at the star centre. I have used a IDL interpolation procedure in order to find the value.

5.18 shows the accordance between theory and observations is not acceptable. This is a further evidence to support the guess that the RRL are off-ZAHB stars.

Thus, after verifying that RRL are evolved stars and obtaining the mean RRL magnitude, one has to correct the latter (that is the observed HB level) taking into account the thickness of the observed HB. I have rescaled the observed HB magnitude shown in the Tab. 5.10 for the difference between the theoretical ZAHB and observed HB in absolute magnitude (see Tab. 5.9). So, I have obtained the correct observed ZAHB level.

Band	ZAHB level (mag)	Absolute Obs. HB level (mag)	Difference (mag)	Rescaled Obs. HB level (mag)
<i>B</i>	0.62	0.54	0.08	15.50
<i>V</i>	0.46	0.29	0.17	15.28
<i>I</i>	0.23	-0.09	0.32	14.98

Table 5.9: The second column shows the theoretical ZAHB magnitudes estimated using the reddest point of the model. The third column is the mean RRL magnitude rescaled to absolute one. The fourth column is the difference between the previous ones and the fifth is the apparent HB magnitude rescaled to the ZAHB level. The latter is then subtracted to the RGB bump level in order to obtained the observed parameter.

Regarding the theoretical ZAHB level, since the ZAHB model does not reach the RRL region for evolutionary reasons, I cannot obtain the value at the mean RRL colour. However, because I have rescaled the observed HB level at the magnitude of the reddest point of the ZAHB model, this problem is removed. The theoretical ZAHB value is outlined in the second column of the Tab. 5.9.

In summary, the observed and theoretical ZAHB magnitude values in the optical bands are shown in the Tab. 5.10. As for the theoretical bump determination, the uncertainties are not shown, because they are estimated for the theoretical ΔV_{HB}^{bump} parameter in the next paragraph.

Band	Observed ZAHB level (mag)	Theoretical ZAHB level (mag)
<i>B</i>	15.50 ± 0.01	0.62
<i>V</i>	15.28 ± 0.01	0.46
<i>I</i>	14.98 ± 0.01	0.23

Table 5.10: It shows the magnitudes of the observed and the theoretical ZAHB for the optical bands.

Figure 5.18: The panels show the CMD in $(V, V - I)$ plane, based on the Stetson's data, with $\mu = 14.65$ mag and $E(B - V) = 0.054$ mag, on which the RRL are overplotted. All panels display four different curves: the Pisa ZAHB, the curves at 50% and 80% of the lifetime in the HB, and the end He locus. From these, it is possible to deduce that the RRL are evolved stars, because they are beyond the 80% of the lifetime in HB. The second panel is a zoom of the first one. The lower panel displays the ZAHB, 50% and 80% of the lifetime locus, moved up to the magnitude level of the less bright RRL.

The Δm_{HB}^{bump} parameter in M30

Before starting the comparison between the theoretical and observed ΔV_{HB}^{bump} , I have provided a quantitative estimate of uncertainties on the predicted ΔV_{HB}^{bump} parameter. The main uncertainties that affects it are: metal and helium content, mixing length parameter, age of the cluster, input physics (as opacity and diffusion). The uncertainties are shown in the Tab. 5.11. They are estimated by Cassisi & Salaris (1997) [15] and Cassisi et al. (1997) [16], except the uncertainty due to age variation. I have determined the latter by comparing the bump position on the isochrones of 11, 12, 13 Gyr.⁵ I have assumed the difference between the bump luminosity on the isochrone of 12 Gyr and one on the isochrones of 11 and 13 Gyr.

All these uncertainties are added in quadrature obtaining a value of $\sim \pm 0.10$ mag.

Parameters	Uncertainties on ΔV_{HB}^{bump} (mag)
Metallicity ($\Delta[Fe/H] = 0.02$)	0.02
Helium content ($\Delta Y = 0.01$)	0.01
Mixing length ($\Delta\alpha = 0.1$)	0.03
Age ($\Delta\text{age} = 1$ Gyr)	0.03
Opacity (5%)	0.07
Diffusion (on/off)	0.05

Table 5.11: Uncertainties on the theoretical ΔV_{HB}^{bump} due to different parameters. The $\Delta[Fe/H] = 0.02$ is the error on the spectroscopic measurement of [Fe/H] given from Carretta et al. (2009) [13] for M30.

I have determined the ΔV_{HB}^{bump} parameter from the difference between the magnitude of the bump and the magnitude of the ZAHB, both theoretically and observationally. I have estimated this parameter, not only for the visual band, but also for the *B* and *I* bands, unlike the literature. The values are shown in the Tab. 5.12 for the optical bands. In the literature, several authors were unable to detect the RGB bump in M30, and thus to estimate the ΔV_{HB}^{bump} parameter: Sandquist et al. (1999) [60], Valenti et al. (2004) [72], Cohen et al. (2015) [21]. Only Di Cecco et al. (2010) [26] have estimated the bump position and the ΔV_{HB}^{bump} parameter. They have found a $\Delta V_{HB,oss}^{bump}$ of -0.45 ± 0.11 mag and a V_{bump} of 14.71 ± 0.05 mag for M30, in agreement with those estimated in this thesis, -0.58 ± 0.11 mag and 14.70 ± 0.04 mag, respectively.

⁵The choice of these isochrones is due to the M30 age estimate and its error: 12 ± 1 Gyr.

Band	$\Delta m_{HB,obs}^{bump}$ (mag)	$\Delta m_{HB,th}^{bump}$ (mag)	Discrepancy (mag)
<i>B</i>	0.02 ± 0.11	-0.42 ± 0.10	0.44
<i>V</i>	-0.58 ± 0.11	-1.01 ± 0.10	0.43
<i>I</i>	-1.30 ± 0.11	-1.75 ± 0.10	0.45

Table 5.12: The second column displays the observed parameters, obtained by the observed HB level rescaled to the ZAHB level. The observational uncertainties were estimated adding in quadrature the errors of the HB level and of the bump position. The third column shows the theoretical parameters with the uncertainties estimated previously. The fourth column displays the difference between two previous columns.

Figure 5.19: Theoretical and observed RGB bump position plotted on the CMD in the $(V, V - I)$ plane, based on the Stetson's catalogue. The theoretical bump is brighter than the observed one. This plot shows the discrepancy between the theory and observations regarding to the RGB bump position.

By comparing the observed and predicted parameters, I have found similar discrepancies larger than 2σ in the *B*, *V*, *I* bands. It shows that the disagreement between theory and observations is independent of the used band. Regarding to the visual band, I have found a discrepancy of ~ 0.43 mag between the predicted and observed ΔV_{HB}^{bump} parameter, in good agreement with the literature. Di Cecco et al. (2010) [26] and Fusi Pecci et al. (1990) [33] have found a discrepancy of ~ 0.4 mag in *V*-band for metal-poor clusters. It decreases moving from metal-poor clusters to metal-rich ones.

This discrepancy is related to the RGB bump position: it is brighter in the theoretical models than the observed one (see Fig. 5.19). It does not depend on the data calibration, because the uncertainties on the reddening and the distance modulus are removed from the difference $m_{bump} - m_{HB}$ of the parameter.

Di Cecco et al. (2010) have excluded the evolutionary models including either α - and CNO-enhancement of helium enhancement as source of the problem, because they do not reduced the prediction-observations disagreement. The discrepancy seems to indicate a problem in theoretical models: the treatment of mixing in the envelope of metal poor red giant stars in the current generation of stellar models is not yet accurate. For this reason, further investigations concerning the input physics adopted in the computation of evolutionary models are necessary before reaching a firm conclusion. More investigations are also required for the metallicity scales, in particular for the possibility of systematic errors when moving from metal-poor to metal-rich GGCs.

In conclusion, I have plotted the ΔV_{HB}^{bump} of several GGCs estimated by Di Cecco et al. (2010), Riello et al. (2003) [55] and the parameter of M30 found in this thesis in a same graphic (see Fig. 5.20). Finally, I have plotted on the data the theoretical line obtained by the BaSTI stellar model [53] at the fixed age (12 Gyr) for α -enhanced chemical compositions. This plot shows the observed ΔV_{HB}^{bump} values are the larger discrepancy for the metal-poor ($[M/H] \leq -1.5$) clusters when compared with the metal-intermediate and the metal-rich ones.

Figure 5.20: ΔV_{HB}^{bump} as a function of the global metallicity $[M/H]$. The used metallicity scale is C09 [13]. The green squares show the parameters from Riello et al. (2003) [55], the black squares are the parameters from Di Cecco et al. (2010) [26] and the blue point is the ΔV_{HB}^{bump} of M30 estimated in this thesis. The red line outlines the BaSTI [53] stellar models at the fixed age (12 Gyr) for α -enhanced chemical compositions. The error bar plotted in the right corner shows theoretical uncertainties.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

In the last decades, the imaging in the infrared has made great progresses, leading to the building of new technologies as the adaptive optics (AO) systems. Thanks to the AO, it is possible to reduce the effect of the atmospheric turbulence on the images, moving close as much as possible to the diffraction-limited imaging. The photometry of stellar fields as globular clusters is difficult because they are crowded stellar systems with about 10^5 stars/pc³. This difficulty can be overcome using the PSF photometry, which is able to distinguish neighbours or partially overlapping stars with more precision. Regarding the infrared photometry, another problem is added: the sky background subtraction. The sky background varies rapidly both spatially and temporally. For this reason, particular techniques have to be developed in order to remove it.

This thesis is focused on the near-infrared (NIR) photometry, in particular on the ground-based data reduction of the old, metal-poor Galactic Globular Cluster M30. The data have been collected in *J* and *K_s*-bands with the instruments SOFI@NTT, MAD@VLT (adaptive optics assisted) and HAWK-I@VLT. First of all, I have performed the instrumental calibration of the SOFI images through the IRAF procedures, correcting them for the instrumental artefacts and homogenising their photometric response. The instrumental calibration is based on the sky background subtraction, necessary to obtain a uniform background on the whole field of view of the scientific images, and the flat field correction, necessary to correct the non-homogeneity of the gain of the pixels and the non-uniformity of the illumination of the detector.

After making the instrumental calibration of the SOFI dataset, I have performed the PSF photometry on 303 frames, covering a field of about 15'x15' around the cluster centre, by means of DAOPHOT/ALLFRAME software. For each image, DAOPHOT automatically selects a number of bright and isolated stars, on which the PSF can be modelled. Then,

ALLFRAME applies the PSF model to all stars on all images, simultaneously, thanks to a non-linear least-square fit.

After performing the PSF photometry, I have obtained two different NIR catalogues of cluster stars, called MAD and SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue, which have to calibrate in order to transform the instrumental magnitudes into standard magnitudes. Indeed, I have separated the MAD photometry from the SOFI and HAWK-I one, because the first could not be calibrated directly through 2MASS standard stars: MAD photometry is deeper and more accurate than 2MASS. Even the faintest stars of 2MASS are saturated in the MAD images and, in addition, the spatial resolution is very different between 2MASS and MAD images. Moreover, the cluster region covered by the MAD images is the centre, where the other catalogue is less accurate. Therefore, I have calibrated: SOFI+HAWK-I on the 2MASS survey and MAD catalogue on the calibrated SOFI+HAWK-I one. They contain 26000 (SOFI+HAWK-I catalogue) and 17500 (MAD one) stars.

Finally, I have obtained the colour-magnitude diagrams in the $(K_s, J - K_s)$ plane. The evolutionary sequences of the MS, SGB, RGB and HB are present in these CMDs. The diagrams show a photometry with an ample range in magnitude: about 7 mag for the SOFI-HAWK-I, 8 mag for the MAD catalogue.

Since the optical data were available, I have extended the NIR catalogues up to the B -band, that is in a spectral range about of $4000 \div 22000 \text{ \AA}$. This permits to have high sensitivity to the effective temperature. I have made it matching the spatial coordinates of each star present in the NIR and optical catalogue, so to have a single catalogue where the magnitudes of each star are shown for all available bands. The optical data used for the cross-match with NIR ones were collected with both ACS@HST and several ground-based telescopes. The used optical catalogues were those of A. Sarajedini and P. Stetson, respectively.

In the second part, I have performed a first data analysis, comparing the observed data with the theoretical models of the Pisa Stellar Evolution Database (Dell’Omodarme et al. (2012) [25]). By the comparison, I have estimated the cluster parameters: the absolute distance modulus, the reddening and the age. The first two have been determined thanks to the use of the theoretical ZAHB, while the age thanks to the isochrones. The distance modulus and the reddening estimates are $\mu = 14.65 \pm 0.10$ mag and $E(B - V) = 0.054 \pm 0.014$ mag, respectively. These values are in agreement with Kains et al.(2013) [41] and Dotter et al. (2010) [30] for the distance modulus (see sec. 5.2), and VandenBerg et al. (2013) [76], Shafly & Finkbeiner (2011) and Dotter et al. (2010) [30] for the reddening (see sec. 5.2). Instead, the age estimate is 12 ± 1 Gyr, in good agreement with the recent literature (Kains et al. (2013) [41], Dotter et al. (2010) [30],

Carretta et al. (2000) [10]. See sec. 5.2).

Finally, I have focused on an evolutionary feature present along the red giant branch, that is the RGB bump. It is a star clustering along the red giant branch on the color-magnitude diagram, due to the crossing of the same luminosity range for three times by the stars during their evolution. This happens when the H-burning shell of a red giant star reaches the discontinuity in the chemical composition left by the convective envelope which had sunk inside the star in previous phases. The analysis of its position reveals a discrepancy between theory and observations, particularly evident for low-metallicity clusters. Since the observed bump position is affected by the uncertainties on the distance modulus and the reddening, I have used the parameter ΔV_{HB}^{bump} (V_{bump} is the apparent visual magnitude of the bump and V_{HB} is the apparent visual magnitude of the HB at the luminosity level of RR Lyrae) in order to avoid them. Therefore, I have searched the RGB bump position and the HB magnitude level, theoretically and observationally. Regarding the observed RGB bump, it was estimated by fitting of the peak of the three-dimensional CMD in the B , V , I , J , Ks bands. I have obtained the theoretical one through the isochrone of 12 Gyr from the difference between the maximum and minimum value in the luminosity variation range in the theoretical plane and respectively in absolute magnitude for each band. Regarding the observed HB magnitude, it can be estimated only in the optical bands, because the HB slope is almost horizontal in these. I have searched the RR Lyrae (RRL) present in the optical catalogue and I have used the mean magnitudes estimated by P. Stetson. I have determined the observed HB level as the mean value of the RRL mean magnitudes. Since the RRL are evolved stars, they do not populate the ZAHB and thus their magnitude has to be rescaled at the ZAHB level in order to compare the theoretical and observed ΔV_{HB}^{bump} (the theoretical one is estimated as magnitude difference between the bump position on the isochrone and the predicted ZAHB level). As the theoretical ZAHB level, I have used the magnitude value of the coolest point near by the RRL region.

Comparing the predicted and the observed parameter, I have found a clear discrepancy between theory and observations: the predicted value is ~ 0.43 mag fainter than the observed one in the V -band. Similar discrepancy is also present in the B and I band, thus this disagreement is independent of the used band. The discrepancy confirms previous results found in the literature which seems to indicate a problem in theoretical models concerning the external convection treatment. Indeed, RGB bump position is brighter in the theoretical models than the observed one and this is independent of the data calibration, because the uncertainties on the reddening and the distance modulus are removed from the calculated parameter. For this reason, further investigations are nec-

essary regarding the input physics of theoretical models and also the metallicity scales, in particular for the possibility of systematic errors when moving from metal-poor to metal-rich GGCs.

The future developments of the current Master thesis project is moving along three different paths:

- NIR photometry: We plan to take advantage of the large number of HAWK-I images available in the ESO archive to improve both the precision and the accuracy of the NIR photometry in the outskirts of the cluster. Moreover and even more importantly, we also plan to take advantage of the NIR images collected with the MCAO (GEMS) available at GEMINI to further complement the photometry of the innermost cluster regions. This means the unique opportunity to identify faint main sequence stars that will allow us to detect the main sequence knee in the low-mass regime.
- UV Photometry: I am also planning to take advantage of both UV ($F336W$) and optical ($F455W$, $F606W$) photometry available in the HST archive to further improve the identification of extreme horizontal branch stars, and in turn the opportunity to use the R-parameter to estimate the helium abundance of this cluster.
- Astrometric selection: The use of both HST and NIR images collected with AO systems will allow us to measure the proper motion of candidate field and cluster stars. This means a substantial improvement in age estimate, but also in the estimate of the structural parameters of this cluster.

Appendix A

Magnitude and Photometric System

Magnitude Definition

Given the monochromatic flux f_λ (energy per unit time, unit area and unit wavelength) at the top of atmosphere coming from an astronomical source, the portion of this flux observed at the telescope within a wavelength range linked to used photometric passband A is described by a quantity called apparent magnitude (Salaris & Cassisi (2005) [59]):

$$m_A = -2.5 \log \left(\frac{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} f_\lambda S_\lambda d\lambda}{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} f_\lambda^0 S_\lambda d\lambda} \right) + m_A^0$$

where λ_1 and λ_2 represent the wavelength limits of the passband, f_λ^0 is the flux of a reference star with apparent magnitude m_A^0 , S_λ is the response function of a given photometric filter in the range λ_1, λ_2 . The definition of the apparent magnitude is a quantity defined with respect to a reference star. Since the apparent magnitude depends on the distance of the object, it is better to define another magnitude independent of the distance, the absolute magnitude:

$$M_A = m_A - 5 \log(d/10pc) = -2.5 \log \left[\left(\frac{d}{10pc} \right)^2 \frac{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} f_\lambda S_\lambda d\lambda}{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} f_\lambda^0 S_\lambda d\lambda} \right] + m_A^0$$

where d is the distance of the object in pc. The different $m_A - M_A$ is so-called distance modulus.

Bolometric Correction

The surface properties of a star predicted by theoretical stellar evolution models are T_{eff} and bolometric luminosity L , which are not directly determined by observations. It is possible to transform the effective temperatures and bolometric luminosities in magnitudes and colour indices, respectively, thanks to some relations called Bolometric Corrections and colour-temperature relations. They are generally produced by convolving models of photometric filter profiles with synthetic spectra of stars (produced as part of the model atmosphere calculations) having a range of effective temperatures, surface gravities and chemical compositions.

We need to determine from L and T_{eff} the flux F_λ of the source at the stellar surface. This is done by using results from model atmosphere computations. They are determined by the chemical composition, gravity and effective temperature. If the distance d is known, F_λ is transformed in flux on the top the Earth's atmosphere by the relation $f_\lambda = F_\lambda(R/d)^2$, where R is the radius of the source.

Assuming $S_\lambda = 1$ at all wavelengths, $\lambda_1 = 0$, $\lambda_2 = \infty$ (that is assuming a magnitude obtained collecting all radiation which arrives on the Earth) and adopting as reference star the Sun, the absolute bolometric magnitude of a star is defined as (Salaris & Cassisi (2005) [59], Girardi et al. (2002) [35]):

$$M_{bol} = M_{bol,\odot} - 2.5 \log(L/L_\odot) = M_{bol,\odot} - 2.5 \log(4\pi R^2 F_{bol}/L_\odot)$$

where L is the luminosity of the source, L_\odot is the luminosity of the Sun, $M_{bol,\odot}$ is absolute bolometric magnitude of the Sun and $F_{bol} = \int_0^\infty F_\lambda d\lambda = \frac{ac}{4} T_{eff}^4$, where a is the black body constant and c is the light velocity.

The bolometric correction is defined as (Salaris & Cassisi (2005) [59], Girardi et al. (2002) [35]):

$$BC_A = M_{bol} - M_A = M_{bol,\odot} - 2.5 \log \left(4\pi R^2 \frac{ac T_{eff}^4}{4L_\odot} \right) + 2.5 \log \left[\left(\frac{R}{10pc} \right)^2 \frac{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} F_\lambda S_\lambda d\lambda}{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} f_\lambda^0 S_\lambda d\lambda} \right] - m_A^0$$

L_\odot and $M_{bol,\odot}$ are known. Therefore, it is necessary to know m_A^0 and f_λ^0 , called zero points of a photometric system. Different choices of reference star in order to obtain the zero points denote different standard photometric systems.

Standard photometric System and Vegamag System

A standard photometric system is a set of specific passbands which defines the standard magnitudes (corrected for the atmosphere attenuation) and the colours for well known stars, distributed over the all sky (Bessell (2005) [6]). The photometric system depends on the set of filters, the detector and the telescope used to obtain the standard magnitudes.

Some astronomers have modified and developed different photometric systems over many years and this have produced several confusion in the literature.

These systems are based on a reference source in order to determine the zeropoints, defined in the previous section. One of the main system of zeropoint is Vegamag system. It is based on the flux of Vega star outside the atmosphere:

$$m_A = -2.5 \log \left(\frac{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} f_{\lambda} S_{\lambda} d\lambda}{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} f_{\lambda}^{Vega} S_{\lambda} d\lambda} \right) + m_A^{Vega}$$

By definition, it is assumed $m_A^{Vega} = +0.03$ at all wavelengths and all colours of Vega equal to zero (Bessell (2005) [6]). Because Vega is a star of northern hemisphere, for the southern hemisphere and sometimes also for the north, the zeropoint is set by an ensemble of unreddened stars of A0 type (as Vega) (Bessell (2001) [5]).

Systems based on Vega flux are the broad-bands Johnson-Cousins (*UBVRI*) and 2MASS (*JHKs*). The *B* band is devised to approximate the photographic response (it is more sensitive to the blue light of the spectrum), while *V* band to approximate the visual magnitude. *U* band is a violet magnitude, obtained by using a violet glass, and it is usually used for very hot stars. The *R* and *I* bands are filters moved towards the longer wavelengths and refer to the Cousins system (Bessell (2005) [6]).

2MASS¹ (Two Micron All Sky Survey) system has uniformly scanned the entire sky in three near-infrared bands *J*, *H*, *Ks*. It was designed to obtain answers to questions on the large-scale structure of the Milky Way and the Local Universe.

¹<http://www.ipac.caltech.edu/2mass/>

2MASS Filters

Figure A.1: Top panel: Johnson-Cousins filters.^a Bottom panel: 2MASS filters.^b^a<http://spiff.rit.edu/classes/phys440/lectures/filters/filters.html>^b<http://www.astro.caltech.edu/~capak/filters/index.html>

Band	Lambda (μm)
<i>J</i>	1.25
<i>H</i>	1.65
<i>Ks</i>	2.17

Table A.1: 2MASS filter system ^a

^a<http://www.ipac.caltech.edu/2mass/overview/about2mass.html>

Band	Lambda (μm)	Bandwidth (μm)
U	0.366	0.065
B	0.436	0.089
V	0.545	0.084
R	0.641	0.158
I	0.798	0.154

Table A.2: Johnson-Cousins filter system (Bessell (2005) [6]).

Appendix B

Stellar Evolution

B.1 HR Diagram and CM Diagram

The evolution of the luminosity L of a star in function of its T_{eff} (it would be the surface temperature if the star were a black body) is described by the so-called stellar evolutionary track. It is the path described in the theoretical $\log(L/L_{\odot})$ vs $\log(T_{eff})$ diagram, **Hertzsprung-Russel Diagram** (HRD), on which the stars evolve along different evolutionary phases. By convention, T_{eff} increases towards the left along the horizontal axis, while the luminosity increases towards the upper along the vertical axis. These evolutionary phases are described in the following section.

The observational counterpart of the HRD is called **Colour-Magnitude Diagram** (CMD), where the star magnitude in a given photometric band is on the vertical axis and the colour index (that is the difference between the magnitudes in two different photometric bands) is on the horizontal axis (Salaris & Cassisi (2005) [59], Castellani [17]). At the first analysis of the CMD, we can notice that the stars take place in well distinct regions of the diagram: the main evolutionary structure is the so-called main sequence, because the lifetime in this region is very long; the remaining stars arrange themselves in the regions brighter than the MS (sub giant branch, red giant branch, horizontal branch and AGB) and in a region fainter than MS (WD sequence).

It is possible to pass from the HRD to CMD or vice versa converting the quantities on the axes thanks to so-called bolometric corrections (See Appendix A).

Figure B.1: Examples of colour-magnitude diagrams: the first is a CMD of the globular cluster M55^a and the second is the CMD of the local stars near the Sun catalogued by Hipparcos satellite.^b

^a<https://apod.nasa.gov/apod/ap010223.html>

^b<http://www.astro.utu.fi/~cflynn/galdyn/lecture10.html>

B.2 Stellar Evolutionary Tracks

The star formation happens in giant molecular clouds presented in the the interstellar medium. Due to different causes, as for example the release of the energy during the

Figure B.2: Models for $Z=0.0006$, $Y=0.230$ and mixing length $\alpha = 2.0$. Left panel: evolutionary tracks in the HR diagram for different mass values. Middle panel: theoretical isochrones in the selected range of ages in the HR diagram. Right panel: theoretical isochrones in the selected range of ages in the colour-magnitude diagram (Cariulo et al. (2004) [8]).

explosion of massive stars, the cloud starts to contract under its own gravitational attraction and the material sunk at the center begins to heat up. The collapsing material forms a dynamically stable core surrounded by the rest of the cloud, called protostar.

When the protostar succeeds to carry away the surrounding gas, it can be called officially star and goes in **Pre-Main Sequence** (PMS) phase. Stars in this phase are fully convective, relatively cold, very expanded (and then very bright). They have not yet reached the temperatures needed to supply the energy losses and to support the stellar structure thanks to the nuclear reaction against the contraction. It does not mean that there are not the nuclear reactions in the PMS stars, but they are not relevant from the point of view of energy production.

After a first evolution in which the star decreases its luminosity and radius at a constant temperature, it begins to form a radiative nucleus and to move to higher temperature until it establishes the nuclear reactions of Hydrogen burning ($T \sim 10^7 \text{K}$). These reactions supply the necessary energy to support the stellar structure and goes in **Zero Age Main Sequence** (ZAMS), first **Main Sequence** (MS) model fully supported by H-burning at the star center in equilibrium conditions in which the secondary elements are at their equilibrium configuration. The star position in HR diagram along ZAMS depends on its mass, because the luminosity and the temperature increase by increasing mass. The

smaller stars ($M < 1.2M_{\odot}$), which burns hydrogen in helium thanks to the pp-chain whose efficiency is proportional to T^4 , take place in the low main sequence; while the more massive stars ($M > 1.2M_{\odot}$), which burns hydrogen in helium thanks to the CNO cycle whose efficiency is proportional to T^{15} , take place in the upper main sequence. Since the GGCs have ages > 10 Gyr, the more massive stars are in advanced evolutionary phases or dead, because their evolutionary lifetime is shorter, and in main sequence only low-mass stars remain. For this reason, I will omit high-mass stars in the upper main sequence in this Appendix.

A low-mass star burns H in a central radiative region, due to small temperature depen-

Figure B.3: In the left panel, it is represented the pp chain; in the right panel, it is shown the CNO cycle (Adelberger et al. (2011)[2]).

dence of the pp chain; while the envelope is convective because the surface temperature is low. During H-burning, hydrogen begins to run low at the center, the total number of free particles decreases and so does the pressure. In order to remain in equilibrium, the star starts to contract slightly and to heat up. The combined effect of the increase of central density and the temperature increase, causes a slow increase of the luminosity of the star.

The central H-burning phase continues until the H at the centre is completely exhausted. This step corresponds roughly to hotter point on the main sequence, called the **Turn-Off** (TO). It marks the end of the central burning phase in low-mass stars. Evolutionary lifetimes during the MS phase are quite long for low-mass stars, about 10 Gyr. Lifetime is a strong function of the stellar mass, decreasing by increasing the mass. At the exhaustion of H at the center as the burning process, the H-burning moves towards more external surrounding regions, in a shell around the He core.

During this phase, the core contracts slowly and the envelope expands. The reason why the envelope expands is unknown. Due to the expansion, the outer layers cool and en-

velope opacity increases (this is inferred by relation $dT/dr \sim k\phi$, where dT/dr is the temperature gradient, k is the opacity and ϕ is the flux): the stellar structure moves in the diagram from the blue to the red side at almost constant luminosity. This is called **Sub-Giant Branch** (SGB) and its evolutionary lifetime is shorter than MS one of about $<10\%$. This evolutionary phase marks the beginning of the **Red Giant Branch** (RGB). Along the RGB, each expansion occurs at almost constant effective temperature (it is dominated by efficiency of convective envelope), while the luminosity increases according to the relation $L \sim M_c^{He}$, where M_c^{He} is the core mass of the star. During the evolution along the RGB, the mass of the electronically degenerate and isothermal core (P depends only on the density) and the central density increases, then the electronic degeneracy becomes stronger and it obstacles the contraction of the star. In a degenerate core, the plasma neutrinos reactions happen: $\gamma_p \rightarrow \nu + \bar{\nu}$. These neutrinos remove energy from central regions. Therefore, the maximum temperature is not at the center but is slightly moved toward outer, in the layers below H-burning shell. When the maximum temperature reaches $\sim 10^8 K$, the He-burning (3α reactions) is ignited. This occurs when the M_c^{He} becomes $\sim 0.5M_\odot$; if the stars do not reach this core mass, they evolve and cool as He-core white dwarfs.

He-burning begins to heat up but, since the core is degenerate, the region does not expand until it is released so much energy to remove the degeneracy. This process is called **Helium Flash**. This marks the end of the RGB phase. The higher point of RGB is called **Tip of RGB**.

After the He flash, the star arranges in a equilibrium configuration at lower luminosity (due to the expansion of the He core after the He flash), where He burns at the interior of He core and the hydrogen burns in a shell with chemical composition similar to the one at the onset of the He flash. The stars go in **Zero Age Horizontal Branch** (ZAHB), first model of **Horizontal Branch** (HB) in which the secondary elements of CNO are at their equilibrium configuration in the H-burning shell. The stars in HB have all the same core mass ($\sim 0.5M_\odot$) but different total mass, because along RGB the stars have lost mass in stochastic processes. Since stars with an more extended envelope have larger opacity and then lower surface temperature, they place themselves towards red side of HRD; while stars with an more extended envelope place themselves towards blue side. The HB luminosity depends on the efficiency of He-burning in the core and the efficiency of H-burning in the shell. The evolution in HB is linked at the H-burning shell efficiency decrease and simultaneously increase of the central He-burning. Since the luminosity produced by the H-burning shell is larger than that produced by He-burning, at the beginning the star evolves towards larger effective temperatures, then, when the

central He-burning process becomes dominant in order to supply the stellar energy, the evolutionary track moves back towards the red side of the HRD.

When the He abundance into the core begins to decrease, the evolutionary tracks move on the HRD towards a lower effective temperature and larger luminosity. He-burning moves towards outer layers of the He core, developing a degenerate core of C/O at the center. This phase is called **Asymptotic Giant Branch (AGB)**, which corresponds to the H and He-shell burning phase. The onset of He-burning in shell causes the extinguishing of H-shell burning due to the expansion and consequent drop of its temperature. Stars with low-mass cannot remove the degeneracy of core and, after reaching the end of the AGB phase, that is **Tip of AGB**, they cool as white dwarfs of C/O-core and go in **White Dwarf Cooling Sequence**. Due to mass losses, the star evolves rapidly towards large temperatures. It continues to burn hydrogen in a thin shell until the star does not reach the bluest point along its evolutionary track at almost constant luminosity. At this point, H-burning is switched off and the star contracts rapidly. Nuclear burning definitively dies out and the remnant cools as a white dwarf.

For this section, I took many information from the books by Salaris & Cassisi (2005) [59] and Castellani [17].

Figure B.4: The stellar evolutionary track for a star mass $1M_{\odot}$. See <http://spaces.imperial.edu/russell.lavery/ast100/Lectures/Ast100Topic25.html>

B.3 Isochrones

The theoretical model which describes a stellar population is called isochrone. It represents the line in HR diagram which connects the points belonging at the different evolutionary tracks of stars being part of the same stellar population at the same time and the same chemical composition, but different initial masses. Therefore along an isochrone, the time is constant but the initial mass changes, unlike the evolutionary track of a single star, where the initial mass is about the same but the time changes along the track. Different sections of a generic isochrone are named as those for the stellar evolutionary phases: the MS of an isochrone is therefore the sequence populated by objects that are still burning hydrogen in their cores. The bluest and brightest point along the isochrone MS is the TO, then it is followed by SGB and RGB phases, until HB (the stars along HB place themselves along a horizontal line) and AGB. After the turn-off, the isochrone coincides with the evolutionary track of the stellar mass at the TO itself, because the lifetime of the evolutionary phases beyond the MS is shorter than MS one. The brightness of the TO of the isochrone increases with the increase of the mass at the turn off itself, because higher masses age more rapidly and are more evolved than lower masses (Salaris & Cassisi (2005) [59], Castellani [17]).

Appendix C

Convection

Convection is a mechanism of energy and chemical element transport. It involves the motion of matter on large scale in the stellar interiors. Matter inside the stars is never at rest, but it is affected by random perturbations around the equilibrium position. Under certain conditions, these perturbations can extend on large scale. Hot gas bubbles rise towards the top, where they cool and fall down as cold gas bubbles. In order to describe the convective transport in the model computation, a criterion for the onset of convection is to search. Since the treatment of this process is very difficult, some approximations have to be made. The flow of gas in a stellar convective region is turbulent, that is the velocity and all other properties of the flow vary in a random and chaotic way. The model adopted is a flow of gas elements with sizes equal in all dimensions. The upward flow covers a mean free path and then dissolves, releasing its excess heat into the surrounding gas. Then, this flow moves downward, thermalizing with the environment. The mean free path is assumed to be the same for all elements and is so-called mixing length. It is defined as (Salaris & Cassisi (2005) [59]):

$$l = \alpha_{MLT} H_p$$

with

$$H_p^{-1} = -\frac{1}{P} \frac{dP}{dr} = -\frac{d \ln P}{dr}$$

where α_{MLT} is a free parameter, a constant calibrated empirically. At the beginning, the bubble will have a pressure, temperature, density and molecular weight equal to those of the environment, supposed to be in radiative equilibrium. An assumption is that the motion of the bubble is fast enough so to consider the adiabatic motion. Along the displacement, the bubble is in the pressure equilibrium with the surrounding gas.

Figure C.1: Illustration of the onset of the convection (Salaris & Cassisi (2005) [59]).

An initial fluctuation of temperature can occur. Consequently, the assumed $\Delta T > 0$ requires that the element (for a perfect gas $\Delta\rho < 0$) rises, because it is lighter than the surrounding material.

$$\Delta\rho = \left[\left(\frac{d\rho}{dr} \right)_{\text{bubbl}} - \left(\frac{d\rho}{dr} \right)_{\text{surr}} \right] \Delta r \quad (\text{C.1})$$

where $(d\rho/dr)_{\text{bubbl}}$ determines the change of the bubble's density, while $(d\rho/dr)_{\text{surr}}$ the change of the density in the surroundings. Δr is a radial shift of the bubble. If $\Delta\rho < 0$, this situation is unstable, since the element is lifted further and the original perturbation increases. In order to transform the gradients of density into those of temperature, the equation of state $\rho = \rho(P, T, \mu)$ can be rewritten in the following differential form:

$$\frac{d\rho}{dr} = \alpha \frac{dP}{dr} - \delta \frac{dT}{dr} + \phi \frac{d\mu}{\mu} \quad (\text{C.2})$$

where $\alpha = (\partial \ln \rho / \partial \ln P)$, $\delta = -(\partial \ln \rho / \partial \ln T)$ and $\phi = (\partial \ln \rho / \partial \ln \mu)$. In this section, we consider the region with homogeneous chemical composition, therefore we neglect the term of the molecular weight μ . Using the equations C.1 C.2 and assuming $\Delta\rho < 0$ $\Delta P = 0$, it is obtained:

$$\left(\frac{1}{T} \frac{dT}{dr} \right)_{\text{bubbl}} > \left(\frac{1}{T} \frac{dT}{dr} \right)_{\text{surr}}$$

If both members are multiplied for H_P , it is obtained:

$$\left(\frac{d\ln T}{d\ln P}\right)_{surr} > \left(\frac{d\ln T}{d\ln P}\right)_{bubbl}$$

Finally, by definition $\nabla_{rad} = (d\ln T/d\ln P)_{surr}$, which describes the temperature gradient when the energy is transported by radiation only, and $\nabla_{ad} = (d\ln T/d\ln P)_{bubbl}$:

$$\nabla_{rad} > \nabla_{ad} \tag{C.3}$$

This is the Schwarzschild criterion. If the equation C.3 is valid, there is the onset of the convection: the temperature of the bubble, after a displacement Δr towards the outer, will be higher than that of the surroundings. Since there is not the variation of the pressure between the bubble and the surroundings, the bubble's density is lower and consequently the element will move towards the surface. When the temperature of the bubble is lower than that of the surroundings, the density is higher than the environment and the bubble moves towards the starting position. On the downward path, the same effect operates but with the opposite sign and, cycle after cycle, the oscillations increase inducing large-scale motions.

The boundary of the convective regions are fixed by the layer where $\nabla_{rad} < \nabla_{ad}$, that is the random motion is not amplified. However, bubbles can cross this formal boundary because they have a non-negligible velocity and then they slow down and halt themselves. This process is called overshooting. The extension of the convection, out the region in which the Schwarzschild criterion is valid, is not still known. A rough estimate based on the mixing length theory provides an overshooting length λ_{OV} either negligible ($\lambda_{OV} < 0.01H_P$) or much more extended ($\lambda_{OV} \sim 0.5H_P$).

The environment gradient ∇ (that is the gradient of the surroundings after that the convection is started) in a convective region has to be higher than ∇_{ad} , that is the convection has to be superadiabatic.

A bubble that dissolves after a path l releases a heat quantity per unit volume $\delta Q = c_P \delta T$, where c_P is the specific heat per unit mass at constant pressure and δT is the temperature difference between bubble and surroundings. δT is proportional to the difference between the adiabatic gradient of the bubble and the temperature gradient in the environment.

In the stellar interiors, the density is so high that the convective gradient can be only negligibly superadiabatic, that is $\nabla \sim \nabla_{ad}$. This simplification is not possible in the envelope, where the gradient is strongly superadiabatic. In this case, the convective gradient is calculated with the mixing length theory, which introduces the uncertainties on

the temperature and radius of the star. This problem is not present in the stellar interiors, because $\nabla \sim \nabla_{ad}$, that is the gradient is determined solely by the thermodynamics, and the convection is not affected by the mixing length.

The assumptions of the mixing length theory are: adiabatic motion of the bubble; hydrostatic equilibrium with the environment; convective column extension $< H_P$; $P_{gas} \sim P_{tot}$. It is assumed that the total energy flux is the sum of the flux carried by radiation and convection at a given layer within the convective region. By neglecting the energy losses during the displacement of the gas bubbles, the convective flux is given by:

$$F_{conv} = \frac{1}{2} \rho v c_P \left[\left(\frac{dT}{dr} \right) - \left(\frac{dT}{dr} \right)_{ad} \right] l$$

where (dT/dr) is the actual temperature gradient in the convective region, v is the velocity of the matter elements that transport the convective flux upwards, $1/2\rho v$ is the flux of mass per square centimetre per second (the factor $1/2$ takes into account half of the matter rises and half falls down at each layer) and l is the mean free path. By using the ∇ , ∇_{ad} and H_P definition, the convective flux can be rewritten:

$$F_{conv} = \frac{1}{2} \rho v c_P \frac{lT}{H_P} (\nabla - \nabla_{ad})$$

This equation can be resolved obtaining the unknown ∇ and v . The velocity of the convective elements can be derived from the equation of motion. The value of ∇_{ad} is provided by the equation of state of the stellar matter. ∇ can be determined by comparison between F_{conv} and the total energy flux.

The radiative gradient is proportional to the energy flux and the opacity. When the energy production by the nuclear reactions has a steep dependence on the temperature, the energy source is concentrated in very central part of the core, where the energy flux is very high. This implies a large ∇_{rad} and then the onset of the convection in the core. On the other hand, the partial ionization in the regions close to the surface implies an high opacity, that favours the onset of envelope convective regions.

This subject is taken from Salaris & Cassisi (2005) [59].

Appendix D

ACS

The Advanced Camera for Surveys (ACS) is a third generation Hubble instrument and was installed during Servicing Mission 3B in 1999. Its wavelength range extends from the ultraviolet to the near-infrared. It is composed by three channels: Wide Field Channel (WFC), High Resolution Channel (HRC is not currently operational) and Solar Blind Channel (SBC). The Wide Field Channel is a high efficiency, wide field, optical and near-infrared CCD camera. It has a field of view of 202×202 arcsec² covering the range from 3500 Å to 11000 Å and a plate-scale of 0.05 arcsec/pixel. WFC is composed by 2 chip of 2048x4096 pixels.

The WFC filters used by Sarajedini are F606W (equivalent wide V of the Johnson-Cousins photometric system) and F814W (equivalent I of the Johnson-Cousins photometric system).

All information is present in <http://www.stsci.edu/hst/acs/documents/handbooks/current/toc.html>.

Array Format	2 x 2048 x 4096 SITe CCDs
Q.E.	77% at 4000Å, 83% at 6000Å, 67% at 8000Å
Pixel size	15μm
Gain	2e/ADU
RON	4.2 ADU
Spectral Response	3500Å to 11000Å
Dark current	0.0062 e/s/pixel

Figure D.1: ACS optical design: Wide Field Channel (ACS/WFC).^a

^a<http://www.stsci.edu/hst/acs/documents/handbooks/current/toc.html>

Appendix E

Core collapse of GGCs

Since M30, the globular cluster studying in my thesis, is a post core collapse, I will mention briefly this process.

The structure of a globular cluster changes slowly with time as a result of simple dynamical principles. A cause of the dynamical evolution of the GGCs is the perturbation of the gravitational field of the system. A typical consequence is the core collapse of the cluster. The gravitational interactions between the stars lead to a velocity distribution of Maxwell-Boltzmann on a time scale, ranged from 10^7 to 10^{10} years, shorter than the age of the clusters (Spitzer (1987) [65]).

The encounters between passing stars can give them a velocity that exceeds the escape velocity, causing the departure of the stars from the cluster and the energy variation. This process is called two-body relaxation or evaporation. As a consequence of star escape, the inner parts of the cluster lose energy and then contract, increasing the central density, the gravitational bound energy and the velocity with which the stars move. In turn, this increase leads to a higher rate of escape and so on. The loss of energy in the inner regions leads to an increase of the kinetic energy, the system becomes hotter (this is explained by negative sign of the specific heat of a self-gravitating object, inferring from virial theorem: $2 \langle T \rangle + \langle W \rangle = 0$ where T is the kinetic energy and W is the gravitational energy of the system. If the system loses energy, W becomes more negative and T increases) and the contraction of the core of the cluster increases. This process is called gravothermal collapse. This collapse will be halted, when a central source generates more energy than lost one by two-body relaxation. A possible source is the formation of close binary with binding energy comparable to the total binding energy of the system. Due to the binary formation, the binding energy increases, i.e. it becomes less negative, and so the cluster expands, because these tight binaries provide energy at the system thanks

to the encounters with other stars. The expansion happens on time scales longer than those for the collapse and can cool the center, leading to an energy flow into the core and to a lowering of core density. An ulterior collapse will follow the expansion phase, and so on, leading a cycle so-called gravothermal oscillation (Djorgovski 1998 [28]).

Globular clusters pass recurrently between a short phase of high central densities and a long phases of low central densities. Therefore, the probability of finding the cluster in low central density states is much higher than in high density states.

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